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BioExcel-2 Project Number 823830

D3.4 – User Community Support and Engagement Report (half-time update)

WP3: Community, Support and Use Cases

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Executive Summary

This report describes work carried out by the BioExcel Centre of Excellence to support and engage with its target user communities during the first 18 months of BioExcel-2, including work done to help ensure that BioExcel activities in all work packages - not only WP3 but also the software and workflow tool development (WP1 & WP2), training (WP4) and sustainability (WP5) - is user driven.

During the first half of 2020, as well as executing COVID-19 related research work (see D3.3 - Use Case Progress Report), BioExcel has adapted to support efforts of the wider computational biomolecular research community to tackle the pandemic, including by facilitating research data sharing, support for

BioExcel is meeting and exceeding stretch targets on all WP3 KPIs, having **supported 600 community members** and **answered 880 questions on the AskBioExcel support forum and GROMACS mailing list during PM1-PM15, and during PM1-PM18 gathered input from 1200 community members** and made available **23 tutorials** to users. The Centre has delivered substantial amounts of support, especially to a well-established and ever growing user base corresponding to the core applications GROMACS, PMX and HADDOCK.

The execution of free energy calculations by combining functionalities of GROMACS and PMX has been confirmed as an area of very strong interest from both academia and industry. Requests for support are accordingly high, and a pilot project with an industrial partner is in the process of being initiated. The high demand suggests opportunities exist for a BioExcel Legal Entity to sustain itself in part by focusing on meeting this demand.

Steps are being taken to support the community in a scalable way by producing tutorials and best practice guides. Workflow tools also play a role, as the containerised execution of large numbers of free energy calculations orchestrated by the PyCOMPSs execution engine to efficiently make use of large-scale parallel HPC resources are enabling rapid massive screening of therapeutics on HPC platforms. As the Use Case work using these tools progresses, the Centre will be able to further leverage the capability demonstrating work done there to support the wider community make use of these tools to perform large-scale free energy calculations.

In contrast to GROMACS, PMX and HADDOCK, there is still not a large user base actively using CP2K for biomolecular simulation using the hybrid QM/MM approach. BioExcel is providing live training sessions and creating, improving and updating tutorials that users can study by themselves to get started using CP2K for QM/MM simulation of biomolecular systems, and is in the process of producing a best practice guide. With regards to the GROMACS-CP2K interface, this is now at a maturity level where it can start to be used for Use Case work as planned in the

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original BioExcel-2 project timeline (see D3.3 - Use Case Progress Report and D1.4 - Project Release of Core Applications). CP2K is simultaneously being optimised for scaling and performance and the interface tested, with work underway to discover and document best practice for joint usage of GROMACS together with CP2K for performing QM/MM simulation including for Use Case demonstrator research work. In the second half of BioExcel-2, the Centre will draw on this experience to support and train the community. In addition to training plans, events are also being planned to help stimulate uptake of CP2K (+GROMACS) for biomolecular research using QM/MM simulation. This is being done by tackling both the hurdle of arriving at a scientifically valid, accuracy-controlled QM treatment of a user's system using DFT, and issues surrounding usage of CP2K's particular implementation of a given DFT approach and how to concretely use the software to obtain meaningful results in an efficient manner, with or without GROMACS.

Surveys of GROMACS and QM/MM user communities have yielded insights that have already helped shape support activities such as the content of best practice guides, and they will continue to do so. Survey results are also feeding into development work, both by direct identification of feature and performance priorities and, in the case of CP2K, by ensuring that the QM/MM benchmarks used to profile and improve the code's performance and parallel scaling include a range of system types, sizes, and model parameters that are representative of the priorities of the user community. Further survey work may also help identify additional opportunities for the Centre to facilitate uptake of workflow tools such as the BioExcel building blocks (bioBB) and the PyCOMPSs execution manager, which in a number of BioExcel Use Cases are key to enabling efficient exploitation of large-scale computing resources to demonstrate how to tackle grand scientific challenges.

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COVID-19

The unexpected spread of the SARS-CoV-2 virus and COVID-19 disease had a dramatic impact on societies across the world. Governments, funding agencies and research groups joined forces to tackle the pandemic. Within the early days of the emerging disease, BioExcel quickly restructured efforts in support of addressing the crisis. In addition to working on specific COVID-19 related research projects (as described in D3.3 - Use Case Progress Report), we focused on facilitating collaborations, extending community support, and providing access to HPC resources at partner centers. Below we highlight some of the initiatives.

COVID-19 Molecular Structure and Therapeutics Hub

We partnered with [MolSSI](#) - a US counterpart to our centre - to jointly create the [BioExcel/MolSSI Molecular Structure and Therapeutics Hub](#). The Hub can be accessed at either <https://covid.bioexcel.eu/> or <https://covid.molssi.org/>. The BioExcel/MolSSI COVID-19 Hub is a community-driven data repository and curation service for molecular structures, models, therapeutics, and simulations related to computational research into therapeutic opportunities for COVID-19.

We worked with large and leading academic and commercial biomolecular research groups, including DE Shaw Research and some of the academic labs that are part of the Folding@Home consortium, to collect and share a wide range of data such as models of small molecules and large assemblies, simulation trajectory data, novel drug targets, etc., which may be useful to the wider community. The portal has quickly become a main reference data resource. It offers a variety of data storage and integration solutions, as follows:

- [GitHub](#) - the simplest storage solution for small molecular data
- [Zenodo](#) - larger data sets of up to 50 GB. We engaged directly with the Zenodo developers on facilitating access for the needs of the portal
- [Amazon Web Services](#) - special allocation has been granted for our COVID-19 data, with no specific limit on the size of the data sets
- [Fenix Infrastructure](#) - we started extensive discussions with the developers for data integration. We have preliminary discussions for adoption of the EBRAINS Knowledge Graph to facilitate data discovery on our Hub.
- [EMBL-EBI COVID-19 data portal](#) - we are in discussions to provide access to the [BioModels](#) and [BioStudies](#) resources

Thus, our portal provides flexibility of storage solutions while offering a single discovery entry point.

Community Letter: Sharing COVID-19 Biomolecular Simulation Data

Sharing of data is vital to the urgent need of lead identification for therapies, diagnostics, and vaccines for COVID-19. To maximize the impact, BioExcel members have signed the international community letter which aims to connect scientists and improve communication between simulation, experimental and clinical data investigators.

Exscalate4Cov Consortium (<https://www.exscalate4cov.eu/>)

KTH and BSC are partners in the newly established consortium bringing GROMACS and HPC consultancy expertise to tailor molecular dynamics simulations for large-scale executions. NBD is screening its proprietary virtual library [ChemistriX](#) as well as other open libraries ([Zinc](#)) and contributes altruistically to the project.

JYU started a number of projects on PRACE and CSC clusters, which are directly connected to COVID-19, and works closely with the research groups of Petri Pihko (expert in organic synthesis) and Varpu Marjomäki (virology specialist).

We have also used BioExcel's position to facilitate connections between the E4C consortium and research groups from EU13 member states, in particular establishing collaborative contacts with academia and the pharmaceutical industry in Bulgaria.

Launch of BioExcel-COVID-19 web-server interface

An online platform - <https://bioexcel-cv19.bsc.es/> - has been launched to provide web-access to atomistic-MD trajectories for macromolecules involved in the COVID-19 disease. The project is part of the open access initiatives promoted by the world-wide scientific community to share information about COVID-19 research.

Website section dedicated to COVID-19

We have added a dedicated section to our website under category Research (<https://bioexcel.eu/covid-19-research/>) to present the various services and activities related to the disease. The services have been promoted to the wider communities in our newsletter along with a call to contact BioExcel for expert support.

Meeting increased demand for HADDOCK

The HADDOCK portal, which allows to model interactions between biomolecules has seen since the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic both an increase in user registration and use of the service. This is clearly seen in Figure I showing the number of unique users per month since the start of the project, with a clear increase from March 2020 onwards.

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Figure I: Number of unique users of the HADDOCK portal per month (these are users who have submitted at least one docking job to the portal).

In order to meet the increased demand, changes have been made to the main HADDOCK Python code that manages the docking workflow, resulting in a decrease of the load on our servers, allowing us to more than double the number of concurrent jobs the server can handle. We have also added to the portals a mechanism to tag submission as being COVID-19 related in order to monitor such submission, but also to redirect the jobs to HTC sites that have committed resources to COVID-19 projects (e.g. the US Open Science Grid, and several high energy physics sites in Europe like the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology and the Centre de Physique des Particules de Marseille). The increased usage of the HADDOCK portal is clearly visible in Figure II, showing the number of processed user submissions per months:

Figure II: Number of users submissions processed by the HADDOCK portal per month (these are users who have submitted at least one docking job to the portal) since the beginning of the project. From April 2020, COVID-19 related jobs are tagged and identified separately.

Introduction

This document describes work carried out by the BioExcel Centre of Excellence supporting and engaging with user communities during the first 18 months of the BioExcel-2 project, including community events organised and work done to help ensure that BioExcel activities are user driven.

In this introductory section we describe the user communities targeted by BioExcel, including how these relate to the core software applications and workflow tools developed and supported by the Centre, and provide a summary overview of the Centre's community support and engagement activities and events. Subsequent sections report details for each user community, and include results and analyses of user surveys.

BioExcel User Communities

Like other Centre activities such as software and workflow tool development and training, our support and engagement activities and the events we organise aim to meet common needs of key biomolecular modelling and simulation communities. These communities encompass common current research areas and techniques of interest to many academic and industrial researchers, as well as innovative state-of-the-art approaches for tackling grand challenges in the life sciences that are enabled by the efficient exploitation of large-scale computing resources. The latter especially are exemplified in the Use Case work done by BioExcel researchers using the Centre's core software and workflow tools, as reported in D3.3 - Use Case Progress Report.

The BioExcel user communities reflect one of the fastest growing portions of users of a range of HPC and HTC infrastructures provided by member states, as outlined in the [PRACE Scientific Case for Computing in Europe 2018-2026](#). The Centre has taken a proactive approach to engaging with these communities to ensure their needs are accurately identified and used to guide our support and development of BioExcel software and associated computational research techniques, thereby ensuring that BioExcel as a whole is user driven.

User community	BioExcel software
Integrative modelling	HADDOCK
Classical molecular modelling and simulation	GROMACS, PMX
Hybrid QM/MM molecular modelling and simulation	GROMACS, CP2K
Workflow tools & standards	BioBB, CWL
Industry	All

Table 1: BioExcel user communities

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For the purpose of describing the support and engagement activities undertaken and events organised by project partners it was found to be useful to consider the division into user communities shown in Table 1. This division is based on usage of techniques and associated BioExcel software, and additionally considers workflow tools and standards as an overarching category and industry as a community with specific needs that warrant separate consideration. Each section of the report following this introduction presents BioExcel's activities relevant to that user community, including survey results and analyses.

Summary of Support and Engagement Activities

WP3 engages in a range of activities to support and engage with the BioExcel user communities. In this section we give a general description of these activities and provide a summary of what has been done during the first half of BioExcel (PM1-PM18), including an indication of the impact these activities have had. Impact is summarised in quantitative terms that typically reflect the number of community members who benefited from the activity. More details about the activities engaged in with regards to each user community and a qualitative assessment of their impact can be found in the relevant user community sections of this report.

Community participation

BioExcel members attend and contribute to community events by presenting scientific results that have emerged from the demonstrator research work described in D3.3 - Use Case Progress Reports as well as advances in the software and workflow tools that the Centre is working to develop. In many cases the scientific results presented have been enabled by the underlying development work, which also paves the way for future research opportunities. These engagements therefore bring the attention of the community to new features and capabilities of the software developed by the Centre and the potential results that can be obtained using appropriate computing resources. These engagements simultaneously serve to connect BioExcel with the community and to gather input on needs and issues relating to software usage in biomolecular research, including by industry. Table 2 shows a summary of community events participated in by BioExcel, excluding events dedicated to training, which are described in D4.2 - Training plan and D4.3 - Progress report and update on training and dissemination plan.

PM	Date	Title	Location	Participants
1	2019-01-30	Face to face meeting with large pharma structural biologists and molecular modellers	Cambridge, UK	3
2	2019-02-25	Online meeting with pharmaceutical industry molecular modellers	online	5
2	2019-02-04	CECAM workshop <i>“Multiscale Modeling from Macromolecules to Cell: Opportunities and Challenges of Biomolecular Simulations”</i>	Lausanne, CH	45
2	2019-02-21	FocusCoE kick-off event	Frankfurt, DE	30
2	2019-02-25	Presentations at University of Oxford on GROMACS and enzyme catalysis using QM/MM EVB	Oxford, UK	30
2	2019-02-25	Presentation on GROMACS software engineering for exascale at <i>SIAM conference on Computational Science and Engineering</i>	Spokane, USA	1000
3	2019-03-11	Pistoia Alliance Workshop on <i>“Application of Bioinformatics in support of Precision Medicine”</i>	London, UK	45

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3	2019-03-01	Presentation at Biophysical Society annual meeting workshop <i>"Working Towards Federating Structural Models and Data"</i>	Baltimore, USA	60
3	2019-03-06	Presentation at Biophysical Society annual meeting workshop <i>"Methods for Integrative Structure Modeling of Biomolecular Systems"</i>	Baltimore, USA	200
3	2019-03-28	Presentation at CompBioMed workshop <i>"Container Technologies in Cloud and High Performance Computing Research and Commercial Applications"</i>	Amsterdam, NL	30
4	2019-04-29	Visit to Beckman Institute at UIUC to discuss improvement of interoperability between GROMACS, NAMD, VMD	Urbana-Champaign, USA	30
4	2019-04-03	<i>"7th CAPRI evaluation meeting"</i>	Hinxton, UK	86
4	2019-04-09	<i>"60 ans du Laboratoire de Biochimie Théorique"</i>	Paris, FR	65
4	2019-04-10	<i>"EOSC-hub week 2019"</i>	Prague, CZ	240
4	2019-04-29	PDC-SeRC lunchtime seminar series	Stockholm, SE	15
5	2019-05-27	<i>"BioExcel Alchemical Free Energy Workshop"</i>	Göttingen, DE	115
5	2019-05-06	<i>"EGI Conference 2019"</i>	Amsterdam, NL	200
5	2019-05-13	Presentations at <i>"Challenges in large-scale biomolecular simulation 2019: Bridging theory and Experiments"</i>	Cargèse, FR	44
5	2019-05-14	<i>"Towards the atomistic-resolution of chromosomes"</i>	Pisa, IT	50
5	2019-05-19	<i>"12th European Workshop in Drug Design"</i>	Siena, IT	
5	2019-05-28	PRACE 6IP WP8 project kickoff	Bratislava, SK	200
5	2019-05-29	<i>"iNEXT workshop Integrated Methodologies and Approaches for Structural Biology"</i>	Brno, CZ	150
6	2019-06-09	Gordon Research Conference: <i>"Computational Aspects of Biomolecular NMR"</i>	Les Diablerets, CH	112
6	2019-06-17	CECAM workshop: <i>"Co-evolutionary methods for the prediction and design of protein structure and interactions"</i>	Lausanne, CH	35
6	2019-06-23	Presentations at <i>"Synergy of experiment and computation in quantitative systems biology"</i>	Nové Hradý, CZ	80
6	2019-06-24	<i>"Workshop in Multi-Scale Modelling"</i>	Leiden, NL	48

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6	2019-06-26	Industrial focus group meeting with SMEs	Barcelona, ES	6
6	2019-06-10	Contribution to <i>"Open Repositories 2019"</i>	Hamburg, DE	30
6	2019-06-14	Presentation at <i>"CP2K Users and Developers Meeting"</i>	London, UK	47
6	2019-06-17	Meetings with vendors, integrators, and large GROMACS user sites at <i>"ISC19 International Supercomputing Conference"</i>	Frankfurt, DE	8
7	2019-07-22	<i>"Asia Pacific Advanced Network Meeting"</i>	Putrajaya, MY	250
8	2019-08-22	Presentations on free energy calculations using GROMACS+PMX at <i>"D3R 2019 Workshop"</i>	La Jolla, USA	75
8	2019-08-25	Presentation on BioExcel Use Case 4 QM/MM work at <i>"17th International Congress on Photobiology"</i>	Barcelona, ES	540
8	2019-08-29	Presentation on BioExcel Use Case 4 QM/MM work and underlying software development at <i>"Finnish Computational Chemistry Days 2019"</i>	Kuopio, FI	70
9	2019-09-03	Presentation on BioExcel Use Case 4 QM/MM work and underlying software development at CECAM workshop <i>"Frontiers in multi-scale molecular modeling of photo-receptors"</i>	Tel Aviv, IL	60
9	2019-09-04	Invited speaker at 7th Annual CCPBioSim Conference - <i>"Frontiers in Biomolecular Simulation"</i>	Bristol, UK	120
9	2019-09-23	Presentation on BioExcel Use Case 4 QM/MM work at <i>"9th International Symposium on Photochromism"</i>	Paris, France	250
9	2019-09-19	Seminar presentation on <i>"CWL - Sharing reproducible computational Analysis"</i> at Cancer Research UK	Alderley Park, UK	15
9	2019-09-24	<i>"Research Object workshop at eScience2019"</i>	San Diego, US	40
10	2019-10-07	<i>"Aviesian symposium"</i>	Paris, FR	100
11	2019-11-17	<i>"Supercomputing 2019"</i>	Denver, USA	11000
12	2019-12-02	Presentation at <i>"Mini-symposium: From coarse-grained to atomistic description of biophysical processes"</i>	Stockholm, SE	40
13	2020-01-14	Large pharma site visit	Alderley Park, UK	1
13	2020-01-21	Online meeting with SME	online	1
13	2020-01-23	Meeting with SME	online	3
15	2020-	Presentation on HADDOCK/COVID activities at <i>"WLCC"</i>	online	53

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	04-02	<i>operation meeting</i>		
15	2020-04-01	CECAM webinar: <i>“COVID-19: challenges and responses in simulation, modeling and beyond - The proteins of SARS-CoV-2, joint data repositories, and community collaborations”</i>	online	~2000 views
15	2020-04-24	EGI webinar: WeNMR - Structural biology in the cloud - 10 years of experience of using EGI services	online	15
16	2020-05-05	Contributions to <i>“Virtual COVID-19 BioHackathon”</i>	online	340
16	2020-05-05	CECAM webinar: <i>“CoVid-19: challenges and responses in simulation, modeling and beyond - HPC and Big Data Approaches in COVID-19 research”</i>	online	~1300 views

Table 2: Community events participated in and organised by BioExcel members during PM1-PM18, excluding events dedicated to training

BioExcel also organises events for the community, which focus both on end users and on application developers. Some events are more training-like, whereas others complement the training programme by creating opportunities for researchers to share results and exchange perspectives on research questions, techniques, and software. In addition to a number of successful training events, the BioExcel-organised “Alchemical Free Energy Workshop 2019” was a particular success in terms of attracting attention from the international biomolecular research community. This event is described in more detail in the section on classical molecular modelling and simulation focusing on GROMACS and PMX.

Like many events in all areas, some BioExcel events due to take place were impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic, such as a joint BioExcel/MolSSI workshop on “Workflows in Biomolecular Simulation” and, substantially, the large BioExcel-sponsored and organised [EMBO workshop: Advances and Challenges in Biomolecular Simulations](#), which was due to take place 18-21 October 2020 in Brno, Czech Republic. The aim of the conference is to bring together top researchers in the fields of biomolecular simulations, integrative modelling, free energy and drug design, workflows and automation and data integration. This will be postponed until 18-22 October 2021.

BioExcel organises regular webinars - details of webinar topics attendees, and benefit to the community in terms of number of views of webinar recordings post delivery (accessed June 28th) are given in Table 3. All in all **736** community members attended BioExcel webinars live, where they had the opportunity to ask questions of the speakers. Follow on YouTube views of all recordings available by PM18 amounted to over **3500** in total.

PM	Title	BioExcel speaker	Attendees	YouTube Views
5	GROMACS 2019 – overview of the new features and capabilities	Y	53	442
6	Prediction of protein-protein interactions in CAPRI	N	24	238

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8	More bang for your buck: improved use of GPU nodes for GROMACS 2018	N	52	206
9	Enhanced molecular simulations with PLUMED	N	50	362
9	Acceleration sampling in gromacs with the AWH method	Y	45	306
11	Software Sustainability - Why and How to do it	N	24	48
12	A walk through simulation parameter options (.mdp files) for GROMACS	Y	96	579
14	What's new in GROMACS 2020	Y	43	363
16	Density guided simulations using GROMACS - combining cryo-EM data and molecular dynamics	Y	89	280
17	Clustering free energy landscapes from molecular dynamics simulations	N	129	598
17	PDB-Dev: A prototype system for archiving integrative structures	N	33	70
18	The HADDOCK2.4 server - new features and a guided demo	Y	83	50
18	COVID-19 Molecular Structure and Therapeutics Hub	Y	15	n/a

Table 3: webinars organised by BioExcel during PM1-PM18

Further details about the community participation activities relevant to each user community, including discussion of their impact and benefits to both the user community in question and to BioExcel, can be found in the report sections for the respective user communities.

In-depth support

BioExcel provides in-depth support for the project's core applications and their usage. We run the [online forum AskBioExcel](#), and use this platform to answer users' queries and keep users up-to-date with other project developments. For part of the project BioExcel ran a separate mailing list supporting GROMACS users, which has been migrated into the AskBioExcel forum. BioExcel staff have also supported users directly through in-person discussion or virtual meetings, or by email. During the period PM1-PM15, almost **600 community members** were supported directly by BioExcel in their usage of core applications through these mechanisms, with around **880 questions answered on AskBioExcel and the GROMACS mailing list**.

BioExcel has also created, improved, and provided tutorials relating to BioExcel software and workflows, and **23 tutorials** were made available to users. These may be used for training through guided practicals or by means of self study, and surveys in fact confirm that users consider these to be a highly valuable and desirable primary form of support material. Details of these tutorials are described in each user community section.

WP3 activities have been undertaken in collaboration with BioExcel staff involved in WP5 to undertake a number of pilot activities with potential industrial partners / future customers to initiate work that has potential to be taken on elsewhere in the project, or in the Centre of Excellence in the future. This has included site visits and virtual meetings with industry researchers to explore opportunities for collaborative work.

Standards and best practice

An important aspect of being part of (and influencing) a wider community is taking part in common activities such as the planning and promotion of standards and documenting best practice. BioExcel participates in community development of standards like Common Workflow Language, along with offering user support and bringing forward standard improvements as identified from user needs, liaising with the code and workflow engine owners for the best technical approach.

BioExcel is producing a set of best practice guides covering use of the main codes of BioExcel and related workflow systems, informed in part by experience gained executing the project's Use Cases (see D3.3 - Use Case Progress Report). While many of the BioExcel codes and workflow tools already have extensive tutorials and reference documentation, these (in particular documentation) can be difficult to navigate, and may often lack the description of know-how that an expert user implicitly follows for how those tools are used or combined to achieve a scientific task. In addition, project-based documentation tends to be specific to a single tool without addressing how to combine tools or choose the right tool. In that sense, while a tutorial aims to show how to do a task, a best practice guide will show why a user would do it, and what reasoning is needed to make the right decisions for

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tool usage, such that results remain scientifically valid. A best practice guide can also be seen as a manual for the manual, as it will naturally link to related tutorials and reference documentation.

To aid discoverability of the guides we will establish a “Best Practices” area on the [bioexcel.eu Knowledge Centre](https://bioexcel.eu), which will link to all our new guides, as well as relevant existing publications, documentation and tutorials. Each guide will be versioned and published as white paper PDFs on [Zenodo’s BioExcel community](https://zenodo.org/), providing citable DOIs; however the guides should be seen as living documents which the Centre and the wider user community is invited to contribute to and keep up to date with current practices. We will investigate open contribution mechanisms such as Google Docs, GitHub pull requests and publishing in the [Living Journal of Computational Molecular Science](https://www.livingjournalofcomputationalmolecularscience.com/).

Outlines for BioExcel Best Practice Guides that intend to capture this know-how for a set of common tasks have been drafted for the core BioExcel Best Practice Guides (BPGs) that are expected to be included as part of the PM24 deliverable D3.5 - Best Practice Guides, namely:

- BPG1: QM/MM using GROMACS+CP2K
- BPG2: GROMACS Best Practice Guide
- BPG3: Writing CWL workflows

BPG1 and BPG2 are due to include reference results on obtaining best performance on a range of architectures relevant to European (PRACE/EuroHPC) HPC systems. The following BioExcel guides are still being considered in planning:

- BPG4: Alchemical free energy calculations based on non-equilibrium sampling
- BPG5: Metaguide to existing best practice guides for using HADDOCK
- BPG6: How to choose which CWL workflow engine to deploy?

The BPGs are described in more detail in each relevant user community section. Building on the experience of BioExcel staff developing the core codes and workflows and providing support and training to users, these guides may also usefully point out “bad practices” or common pitfalls observed in practice, or highlight the scientific challenge that motivated a particular feature.

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Whilst individual guides will be tailored to its particular community and tool, a common structure has evolved that may be suitable for several of the guides:

1. Introduction:
 - a. Rationale for using method X
 - b. Overview of X implementations
2. Recommended work pattern
 - a. System preparation (e.g. choice of methods, data sources)
 - b. Simulation/execution
 - i. Choice of input parameters, execution considerations
 - c. Post-processing or analysis
 - i. Statistics, validation
 - d. Checklist of main steps to successfully run X
3. Common pitfalls and limitations of X
4. Recommended resources, tutorials, bibliography
5. Conclusions
6. References

User & community needs analysis and feedback

The needs of the user communities are continually changing. It is important for BioExcel to have efficient means to capture and analyse the needs of the various user communities so they can be used to steer the activities of the project. Much of this happens organically through engagements of staff with relevant communities directly informing the work they are doing. But in order to ensure that BioExcel is truly user driven, we have developed and implemented some more formal methodologies to capture insights arising from many distinct meaningful engagements with users of BioExcel tools and services where we gain their opinion on certain topics. The underlying model for this process is depicted in Figure 1.

These engagements and methodologies take many forms, including online surveys (e.g. using SurveyMonkey, Google Forms or Jisc Online Surveys), Q&A sessions, Twitter polls and discussions, in-depth interviews with users, discussion groups or focus groups, polls or surveys during webinars, post-training-event feedback forms, questionnaires, informal in-person interactions at events, etc. Findings from these have been fed back to the wider project, including both the technical work packages (WP1/WP2), training (WP4), and the sustainability WP (WP5).

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Figure 1: Generic process for engaging and gathering feedback from various users and communities followed by resulting actions to ensure that BioExcel is user-driven.

During the first 18 months of BioExcel-2 the Centre has **gathered input from over 1200 community members** through a combination of the above mechanisms. This input has consisted roughly half of fixed format community surveys targeting existing and potential users of GROMACS, QM/MM, and the HADDOCK web server, and half of a variety of mechanisms including in-depth interviews and one on one meetings with community members from academia and from industry, with 157 from industry of the latter having provided input in some way.

For each user community, we include results and analyses of any user surveys that were run and findings from any other engagements, as well as discussion of how these have guided the Centre's support and engagement activities.

Integrative Modelling (HADDOCK)

Community participation

Participation in the Critical Assessment of Biomolecular Interaction (CAPRI) experiment. CAPRI is similar to CASP but geared toward the prediction of biomolecular complexes. Blind predictions have to be made, that allow an unbiased evaluation of the state of the art in the field. The UU HADDOCK team has been participating in CAPRI since 2003. In the current reporting period, the UU team participated in rounds 48 and 49, in both prediction and scoring parts.

- Presentation on *“Integrative modeling of biomolecular complexes”*. CECAM workshop: "Challenges In Large Scale Biomolecular Simulations 2019: Bridging Theory And Experiments". Cargèse, Corsica, France, May 13-17, 2019.
- Presentation on *“Integrative modeling of biomolecular complexes: from small molecules to membrane systems”*. iNext workshop on Integrated methodologies and approaches for structural biology. Brno, Czech Republic, May 29-31, 2019.
- Presentation on *“Integrative modeling of biomolecular complexes”*. EMBO workshop on synergy of experiment and computation in quantitative systems biology. Nove Hradý, Czech Republic, June 23-28, 2019.
- Presentation on *“Distinguishing native from non-native poses of HADDOCK using GROMACS”*. BIOMOS meeting Ausserberg, Switzerland, September 2019.
- Presentation on *“Integrative modeling of biomolecular complexes”*. CECAM BIIMMS 2019 school. Lugano, Switzerland, October 7, 2019.
- Presentation on *“Integrative modeling of biomolecular complexes”*. Aviesan symposium on Deciphering the Functional Mechanisms of Biological Macromolecules. Paris, France, October 8, 2019
- Presentation on *“Integrative modeling of biomolecular complexes”*. From Protein Complexes to Cell-Cell Communication. Esztergom, Hungary, October 27-29, 2019.
- Presentation on EMBO practical course on *“Practical Integrative Structural Biology”*, Hamburg, Germany, November 3-8, 2019
- Presentation on *“Integrative modeling of biomolecular complexes”*. GIDRM meeting on Computation methods and NMR spectroscopy: A powerful synergy for chemistry, materials science, and biology. Pisa, Italy, December 10, 2019.
- Presentation on *“HADDOCK workshop on Integrative modeling of biomolecular complexes”*. Coimbra University, Portugal, December 18-19, 2019.
- Presentation on *“Integrative modeling of biomolecular complexes”*. Applied Bioinformatics in Life Sciences, Leuven, Belgium, February 13-14, 2020.

In-depth support

The HADDOCK team offers support and consultancy to users on an ongoing basis via the AskBioExcel forum and by responding to requests sent directly to individual HADDOCK developers or to haddock.support@gmail.com. These support mechanisms alone already amount to more than 350 users supported at the very least during the period PM1-PM15, in addition to which the team supports many users through informal in-person interactions at events. The team has also been advising and supporting research groups at a number of institutions, including Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais - UFMG, Belo Horizonte, Brazil; the EMBL in Heidelberg, Germany, the NMR team at Dana-Farber Cancer Institute at Harvard Medical School, and a structural biology group at the University of Pittsburgh. The team is further establishing support to University of Connecticut in refining SAXS models with HADDOCK.

Standards and best practice

All HADDOCK tutorials, method papers or scientific reports have been collected in order to create a comprehensive best practice guide for various docking scenarios. HADDOCK tutorials have been updated and extended for the new 2.4 version, and a manual for HADDOCK 2.4 is being prepared. In these tutorials and in the manual, new HADDOCK features are described in detail in response to user requests from our survey.

HADDOCK2.4 web server user survey

A survey was held amongst users of the [new HADDOCK2.4 web server portal](#), and the results and analysis of this survey are presented here. Out of a total of 229 respondents, 99% of users reported successful job submission and 90% of users would describe the webportal as friendly and reliable. Some user suggestions have already led to improvements of the portal with new features implemented in response, for example the functionality for structural visualisation of interacting residues was added in response to the following user comment:

- *“It would be nice to include some small 3D visualization windows where the submitted structures can be seen and maybe the active/passive residues are highlighted at the surface.”*

A request from a user to create a web server portal to run [pdb tools](#) was also acted on in response to the survey and made available to users. New tutorials for HADDOCK2.4 have also been created, as well as a manual explaining all new features. Highlights of verbatim comments from users in answer to the question “What would you suggest to improve?” with regards to HADDOCK2.4 are listed below:

- *“It is pretty good as it is.”*
- *“Pop-ups that give a short explanation to the options during the input, or suggestions when to consider changing a certain value”*
- *“I had one issue, where if you have a slight error in naming or whatever, it redirects to the problem that is amazing. The slight problem lies in that you have to select your pdb files again. Not a big deal-breaker for me just a slight inconvenience.”*

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- *"Its perfect."*
- *"I found the short explanations on the right side of the input mask really helpful. Although this doesn't replace a Tutorial it is a good remainder of data requirements if you are an irregular user. Extending this explanations to more field would be helpful."*
- *"It's all good as it stands. As a novice user, I find the software and the interface very user-friendly."*
- *"Overall, it is very great and very useful server. I have a minor comment. Sometimes, I will resubmit my previous job with minor revision. If there is a way to recall previous parameter and modify them, and then submit it, so user don't need to start from scratch every time. Thank you!"*
- *"Nothing; the portal is really clear and user-friendly, even for a student like me."*
- *"None, it is very user friendly"*
- *"It's very good already"*

We also asked users if they had previously used the older version 2.2 of the portal and how the new portal compared to it - see Figure 2.

Figure 2: user satisfaction with HADDOCK web server portal version 2.4 compared to the older version 2.2. Higher score indicates preference for the newer version.

Users could also comment on why they like the new version and some of the comments are listed below:

- *Visualization the molecules, and parameter selection availability.*
- *Much more friendly user interface and great that it checks the PDB files before you fill in the rest of the job parameters, stops you submitting jobs that just stumble at the first hurdle.*
- *Everything is easier, visually much nicer, course grain docking is a great addition. Like the way it checks for errors as you move through the submission pages.*

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- *easier to assess issues with pdb, constrains, ...*
- *the residue selection is much better*
- *I used the haddock 2.2 and tried to submit my job but came up with errors for about 3 hours before I actually figured out what was going on. The 2.4 interface was much clearer and immediately explained to me everything I was doing wrong on the 2.2 server.*
- *Far fewer clicks required to load up a run - luxury!*
- *It is pretty good.*
- *I didn't use the old portal but love the new one*
- *I really feel that visualization of active/passive residues on protein cartoon is very good and it gives much better impression where the docking is going to happen.*
- *Very professional and user-friendly interface; very visually appealing; easy to understand and change parameters*
- *The graphical interface of Haddock 2.4 portal of nicer than previous and all the options available are presented, with well-organized sections and sub-sections*
- *the new version of HADDOCK2.4 is more user - machine interaction*
- *more user friendly interface; showing the active and passive residues on the structures; integrating different interfaces,*
- *It is great to know when an error occurs before filling out all the parameters, i like the visualization of the docking site as well.*
- *Now, You can send multibody docking or standard calculations from the same portal. I like the interface and some options are also more easy to find*
- *For a novice user it is a bit clearer since there are also some explanations provided. Also, the visualization of molecules helps.*
- *previous Version require to go through extensive editing of the PDB files, current version is user friendly and fast*
- *The ability to visualize active residues specified.*
- *very user friendly*
- *The progress bars are a great addition*
- *The website interface is much more user-friendly and it is easier to understand every step of the process and not make mistakes in this step wise manner.*
- *ood to have a single interface rather than "basic" "expert".. good to have a "wizard"*
- *more easy to run a job*
- *This such a nice web-server to work on CADD related projects. Thanks.*

Based on the above and on the answer to the question in Figure 3, the survey reveals that the new HADDOCK2.4 web portal, which is a completely new design, is well appreciated by both old and new users.

Figure 3: >90% of users would recommend the new version to collaborators

Classical Molecular Modelling & Simulation (GROMACS & PMX)

Community participation

The GROMACS team has given a series of webinars, comprising introduction of new features in the 2019 and 2020 releases of the software, best practices on how to use simulations parameter settings in general, and, in particular, for the accelerated weighted histogram method, and on density-guided simulations with GROMACS. These were popular webinars, with a combined live attendance of 326 people and around 2000 YouTube views by PM18. BioExcel webinars at which speakers external to BioExcel presented on topics relevant to the classical molecular modelling and simulation community covered PLUMED and clustering free energy landscapes from molecular dynamics simulations, which together had 179 live attendees and around 1000 YouTube views by PM18.

Members of the GROMACS team took a leading role in the “*PRACE-XSEDE-RIKEN International HPC Summer School*”, the “*Advanced GROMACS, HADDOCK + PMX Workshop*”, the “*Data sharing from Molecular Simulation workshop*”, and taught on the BioExcel Summer School.

Members of the GROMACS team were present at community events, the HPC conference Supercomputing 2019, “*Mini-symposium: From coarse-grained to atomistic description of biophysical processes*”, and the BioExcel Alchemical Free Energy Workshop 2019 (see [BioExcel-2 Dissemination and Training events](#)).

The [Alchemical Free Energy Workshop](#) took place on May 27-28, 2019 in Goettingen, Germany. The event received a lot of attention in the community of computational chemists and attracted 115 participants. 16 speakers were invited to the workshop and in addition 8 registered participants were selected to present.

The workshop managed to catch the interest of both academics as well as scientists working in the pharmaceutical and software development industry. Mostly positive feedback was received from the participants after concluding the workshop. A detailed report on this meeting is included as an appendix at the end of this document. Based on the success of the *Alchemical Free Energy Workshop 2019*, future collaboration on a biannually alternating event was planned together with the computational chemistry community in the US. Tentatively, the next event in Europe would be set in 2021.

In the BioExcel Summer school 2019 in Pula, Italy, alchemical free energy calculations and PMX were presented in a lecture and subsequent hands-on tutorials. Free energy calculations and the PMX software were also presented in the CECAM workshop “*BImBS 2019 - BioInformatics meets BioSimulations in protein and DNA studies: from theory to practice*” that took place from 5 to 12 October 2019 in Lugano, Switzerland. A lecture was given on the theoretical

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aspects of alchemical free energy calculations, as well as demonstration of the applications of these approaches for various biomolecular systems. Following the lectures, the participants could join hands-on tutorials on the free energy calculations based on molecular dynamics simulations.

In-depth support

GROMACS

In-depth support has been carried out on multiple levels, comprising forum, mailing list, personal interactions, specialist tech support and site-visits.

The KTH GROMACS team supports users directly through conversations on the users and developers mailing lists, with more than 500 unique issues addressed in the first year of BioExcel alone. To better support users, the user mailing list has moved to a more modern forum format with extended capabilities. We have successfully moved a large user base, reaching the same level of activity of ca. 25 topics per week only two weeks after the move.

To concretely feed back user issues into the development cycles, forum topics were cross-linked to issues logged in the development platform GitLab, and these were tagged “request” to signal to the developers where and how users envision improved functionality.

The most insightful user interactions happen at face-to-face meetings at conferences, and these directly inspire development work. To better use this resource, we have carried out in-depth interviews with participants at the *“PRACE-XSEDE-RIKEN International HPC Summer School”* as well as at the *BioExcel Summer School 2019* about their use of GROMACS and on their needs regarding development of the code. Insights have aided in shaping an initial draft of the GROMACS user survey.

A distinct type of users are administrators of compute-centers that often require more specialised and extended support efforts to compile and install GROMACS in a way that makes the most use of very specialised hardware resources. These interactions typically lead to long-standing collaborations and insights for on both sides: by fine-tuning on current GROMACS versions, developers learn about the scaling and performance of GROMACS. Simultaneously, GROMACS developers give advice on the best hardware setup for performing simulations. This type of in-depth support was carried out, amongst others, with industry partners, CSC in Finland, and the University of Oxford in the United Kingdom.

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PMX

PMX support is implemented on different levels ranging from email support to face-to-face interactions at conferences and workshops. Bug reports, feature requests and troubleshooting run mostly via email, whereas higher level discussions on development are better suited for face-to-face or video interaction. At the *Alchemical Free Energy Workshop* in May 2019 over 100 practitioners and developers of alchemical free energy calculation approaches met in Göttingen, many of which were actively using PMX. These and similar training events at CECAM, the *BioExcel Alchemical Free Energy workshop* and on site with Janssen Pharmaceutica provided the most detailed interactions with users, giving insight into their needs as well as challenges faced, and thus helped develop strategies for future code development, streamlining of installation and dealing with different levels of user interaction ranging from interactive to large-scale automated batch processing.

By extending a collaboration on relative binding free energies with Janssen, MPG is working with the Open Force Field consortium on protein-ligand free energy calculations. Together with Janssen, protein-ligand binding free energy automated workflows are being created and a benchmark set being assembled.

Standards and best practice

KTH and UU have contributed together with external authors to the publication [“Sharing Data from Molecular Simulations”](#) that collects best practices around data handling and file sharing. The GROMACS team contributed to best practices on data sharing and file formats in this context.

Within BioExcel, we harmonised, updated and shared molecular dynamics simulation setups best practices with all use case scenarios, where molecular dynamics simulations were involved. This is also reported in D3.3 - Use Case Progress Report.

MPG has plans to prepare a best practice guide for the non-equilibrium alchemical free energy calculations. A potential dissemination channel is the LiveCoMS journal (Living Journal of Computational Molecular Science).

UEDIN is due to produce a best practice guide covering best practices for key steps involved in preparing, performing, and analysing generic MD simulations with GROMACS as well as a best practice guide for usage of more specific/advanced functionalities present in GROMACS including a range of enhanced sampling techniques, and finally optimal parallel execution options. The guide will provide reference benchmark results for a range of systems on a range of platforms (including with and without GPUs) that provide users with guidance on optimal parameter choices for performance relevant to PRACE/EuroHPC architectures.

In-depth interviews

We carried out extensive person-to-person interviews, each lasting around 30 minutes. These interviews were based on a set of guiding questions and then evolved freely. We found that application areas varied widely from nano gold wires to classical molecular dynamics on bacteriorhodopsin to silicium surfaces and coarse-grained models. Challenges that users faced were translated into developer issues. A large part of the issues that users named during the interviews pointed rather at the larger molecular dynamics simulation community. These issues were often related to file format standardisation, molecule topology naming conventions, force field and method naming harmonisation - a large part of which had been brought up by participants at the BioExcel workshop “*Sharing Data from Molecular Simulations*”.

Another common topic was the setting of simulation parameters (.mdp options). In response to this, we provided a [webinar](#) to provide guidance.

Guiding questions:

- What MD engine do you use?
- What system did you simulate last?
- What do you remember as most annoying performing the simulation?
- What do you remember was difficult when performing your first ever simulation?
- Does performing a simulation still take the same effort for you as it did in the beginning? (If not, where have you become faster in running simulations?)
- How did you generate the data for your latest Figure that represented some simulation results?
- What support or sources of information did you refer to to help you set up or run the simulation?
- How could this support or these resources be improved?
- One wish for the simulation community?
- Name / Affiliation / Career stage

GROMACS online community survey

To ensure the work done by BioExcel is user driven, an online survey was conducted in the biomolecular simulation community to better understand the needs of researchers with regards to use of GROMACS. The survey was distributed directly within the community of known GROMACS users and to the wider biomolecular simulation community, and targeted researchers ranging from those with no experience using GROMACS to expert GROMACS users. The survey sought to identify the most commonly time-consuming and/or frustrating difficulties encountered by all GROMACS users and to understand whether they were able to find and make use of support resources to help them resolve any issues encountered. The survey additionally sought to identify GROMACS functionality or performance felt to be lacking or most thought in need of improvement by

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experienced GROMACS users. A further set of questions was asked of respondents currently working or having previously worked in industry, these are reported on separately in the industry section of this deliverable.

The goal of the survey was to provide clear views on the most pressing needs of researchers using GROMACS, on the research topics and types and sizes of biomolecular systems being studied, and on the computing resources being used to execute simulations on. The findings were used to gauge the effectiveness of existing BioExcel work and to prioritise ongoing GROMACS development work and the provision of training and support, including the planned content of a GROMACS best practice guide.

Respondent backgrounds

The survey received 287 responses, mainly from academia:

Figure 4: responses to the question “What best describes your current work?”

As shown in Figure 5, survey respondents consisted of a large number of researchers with intermediate and expert levels of experience using GROMACS and smaller numbers of novice and completely inexperienced GROMACS users. Out of respondents who said they had never used GROMACS, three said this was because they found it in some way difficult or daunting to start doing so, whilst for most others GROMACS was inherently not directly useful in their work.

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Figure 5: responses to the question “Which best describes the amount of experience you have using GROMACS?”

Systems studied

Respondents were asked which biomolecular systems or core system constituents they study through simulation, and were free to choose as many options as relevant from a predefined list as well as to specify others. Results as a percentage for each of the main user cohorts (expert, intermediate, novice) as well as for all respondents are shown in Figure 6 in decreasing order based on the latter. Under “other” there were two identifiable categories with multiple responses, namely polymers, followed by ionic liquids. Broadly speaking, more experienced users were more likely to report studying any system. Expert users were significantly more likely to study saccharides/carbohydrates, DNA, RNA, and lipids, even compared to intermediate users. Novice users were significantly less likely to study these systems and also surfaces and metalloproteins, but more likely to study nano-structures (e.g. carbon nanotubes) than intermediate users.

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Figure 6: responses to the question “Which of these best describe the most important, core components of the systems you are trying to simulate?”

System sizes

A question asking the typical size of systems being simulated by respondents yielded the results shown in Figure 7. For every experience cohort the most common system size simulated is around 100 000 atoms. Broadly speaking more experienced users are more likely to simulate systems larger than this and less likely to simulate smaller ones.

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Figure 7: responses to the question “What is the size of your typical simulation?”

Research topics

Asking respondents what research topics or properties they investigate through simulation yielded the responses shown in Figure 8. Under “other”, several respondents reported an interest in studying conformational changes. Broadly speaking more experienced users were more likely to be interested in any given property or research topic. Expert users were significantly more likely than even intermediate users to be interested in computing solvation/hydration free energy/enthalpy/entropy, and somewhat more likely to be interested in biomolecular structures/structure refinement, and binding kinetics. Novices were less likely to be interested in all properties and topics, especially multiphase systems, but equally interested as experienced and intermediate users in computing binding affinity.

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Figure 8: responses to the question “What properties are you interested in simulating?”

Compute platform

When asked which single compute platform they typically used to run simulations, a slightly larger percentage of all respondents said they typically use a local compute cluster belonging to a research group or university or comparable - categorised as Tier3 or less in the HPC hierarchy - than said they used a large HPC cluster (Tier2 or greater). To place the survey results and analysis into their proper context with regards to what is relevant for exascale usage of GROMACS, it is worth noting that although a slightly larger number of users use a local cluster rather than a large HPC cluster, the only slightly smaller fraction of all users who typically use a large HPC cluster correspond to usage of a much large amount of resources (corehours), i.e. the above distribution should *not* be read as directly reflecting corehours used on each system by GROMACS users.

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Figure 9: responses to the question “Where do you usually perform your simulations?”

Accelerators

A high percentage (86%) of all GROMACS users reported using GPUs to perform simulations or intending to do so, with an only slightly lower 82% of novice users reporting this to be the case. GPU vendors were represented amongst respondents as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: responses to the question “Which brand of GPU do you use?”

Usage of NVidia GPUs was high (>90%) amongst all groups apart from novices and especially amongst expert users, which may reflect in part the predominance of

NVidia accelerators on the current generation of large HPC machines. We anticipate that this predominance may shift to include a somewhat higher percentage of AMD GPUs in future as these gain increased traction in HPC (it is possible for example that the EuroHPC Lumi system may incorporate AMD rather than NVidia GPUs as will be the case in upcoming US-based HPC machines Frontier and El Capitan).

User time & frustration

Respondents were asked to rank key steps preparing, running, and analysing simulations using GROMACS in order of the amount of time they typically take to perform, yielding the responses in Figure 11.

Figure 11: responses to the question “Thinking of your typical simulation, which steps do you spend the most time preparing?”

Broadly speaking, choosing forcefields and preparing the GROMACS parameter (mdp) input file were on average ranked as taking the least time compared to other steps, both within each cohort and for all respondents taken together. For novice users launching and troubleshooting simulations was strongly ranked as most time consuming compared. For expert and intermediate users and for all respondents taken together, postprocessing and analysis of simulation results using GROMACS tools was ranked as taking most time compared to other steps. The likelihood of respondents ranking this step as the most time-consuming increased with degree of experience, with 49% of expert GROMACS users listing it as their most time-consuming step, a higher proportion than any step ranked by any group. This is in contrast to mdp file preparation and simulation launching & troubleshooting, where average time ranking reduces with increased experience. Analysis showed that the variance in time ranking across all steps was greatest for expert users and diminished for less experienced users, implying strongest cohort consensus amongst expert users’ ranking of relative time cost of different steps, and diminishing consensus for less experienced users. Users were next asked to

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rank the same steps according to how frustrating they typically found them. These results, in Figure 12, look broadly similar to the time ranking responses in Figure 11.

Figure 12: responses to the question “Thinking of your typical simulation, which step frustrates you the most?”

It is more instructive to look at the differences between respondents’ average frustration rankings and average time rankings - see Figure 13, in which a positive difference value indicates greater average frustration ranking than average time ranking for that step, and vice versa for negative values.

For all cohorts considered together, there was strongest concordance between frustration and time rankings for what were judged on average to be both the least time-consuming and least frustrating steps, namely choosing force fields and preparing the mdp file, followed by system (e.g. PDB) preparation. Novice users ranked these steps as somewhat more time consuming than frustrating, especially mdp file preparation, whereas more experienced users found these steps somewhat more frustrating than time consuming, especially expert users for system preparation.

Experienced users, intermediate users, and all users taken together found launching and troubleshooting simulation execution far more frustrating than time consuming, though this was not true by novices. Experienced (expert and intermediate) users ranked the two most time-consuming steps, namely checking of raw results and postprocessing/analysis using GROMACS tools, as significantly less frustrating than time consuming. However this was not matched by novices, who ranked checking of raw results as roughly equally frustrating as time consuming but postprocessing/analysis with GROMACS tools as more frustrating than time consuming.

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Figure 13: subtractive difference between frustration and time spent (positive values imply higher frustration ranking than time cost ranking)

Asked what single factor was most likely to cause frustration, users responded as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: responses to the question “Thinking of the step you rated most frustrating, why is this step so frustrating?”

Experienced (expert & intermediate) users found task repetitiveness to be the leading cause of frustration. This was only of secondary importance to novice users, who overwhelmingly reported the struggle finding documented information they needed to be able to use the software to be their leading cause of frustration. Further questions in the survey discussed below clarify how users go about finding help, documentation, support, and guidance for using GROMACS,

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and thereby helped identify how BioExcel can best address this source of frustration. Documentation and ease of use were secondary causes of frustration for experienced users, with intermediate users more likely than expert users to be frustrated due to perceiving GROMACS as not being easy (intuitive) to use. Software performance was least likely to cause frustration, and the less so with increasing expertise level (possibly reflecting an earlier identified tendency for expert users to be more likely to be running on large HPC machines).

Free form optional comments addressing the question of causes of frustration supplied by respondents on this topic included:

From novice users:

- *as a beginner I often make mistakes that lead to crash of my simulation*
- *You will have to wait until the simulations is finished which take days and then try to check if your system is stable and the output is reliable if not, then you have wasted the whole simulation time and then you have to try another trial after being upset from the time lost.*
- *Can't do what I want to do. Analysis scripts too limited*

From intermediate users:

- *finding good forcefields for solvents other than water is a nightmare, forcefields often need to be tweaked heavily*
- *With complex systems, it is very easy to go wrong with the initial input coordinates. Requires a lot of care. The most important and frustrating step.*
- *Almost always need to code additional analyses*
- *I use gmx tools for basic analysis, but often you need something more, which is fine*
- *Typos, structure of .top and .itp files, understanding well the output of gmx tools*
- *Polarizable FFs should be implemented (AMOEBA, Drude,...)*

From expert users:

- *Choosing consistent potential models needs large literature search, building new models takes many efforts*
- *I do force field development, so not really a gromacs problem*
- *usually it's about the validity of the setup, not the software itself*
- *comparing force fields and selecting the most appropriate one, mostly unrelated to GROMACS but can involve having to convert between formats*
- *My systems are fairly non-standard and can take some work to get running properly - not GROMACS's fault*
- *Analysis tools*
- *I didn't know what the MD input script was meant to be. I think the most frustrating aspect is the changes between versions when you're teaching students they can't follow your tutorials or we can't work together if we have different versions installed. Cpt file incompatibility too*
- *It just takes several iterative steps to fix structure for GROMACS parametrization tool: exclude gaps, non-canonical residues, etc.*
- *Difficult to implement nonequilibrium simulation*

Finding documentation & support

When users were asked what they would do to find out how to use particular GROMACS functionality (e.g. a command) unfamiliar to them, responses were as shown in Figure 15.

D3.4 – User Community Support and Engagement Report (half-time update)

Figure 15: responses to the question “When you do not know how a command works, where do you go to find the answer?”

All users were most likely by far to perform a direct internet search, followed closely by seeking out a description of the relevant command in the GROMACS manual. Asking a colleague for help was the next most frequent way of finding help, by a fairly wide margin. Responses were remarkably similar for all user cohorts, with the exception of finding BioExcel webinars (the least taken action overall), which users were more likely to do the less experience they had. This may be due to newer users having begun using GROMACS during BioExcel-1 or indeed BioExcel-2.

Learning to use GROMACS: usage of training/support resources

Newer users - novices and those just starting to learn GROMACS - were asked to rank how useful they considered a number of different support and training resources in helping them learn how to use GROMACS - see Figure 16. It was clear that tutorials (concrete “How To’s”) were considered by a strong majority of novice users to be very useful for learning how to use GROMACS, much more so than any other training/support resources. This confirms a finding also recognised in a separate survey performed by BioExcel regarding QM/MM simulation. Lists frequently asked questions (FAQs) were considered by a strong majority of novice users to be somewhat useful.

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Figure 16: responses to the question “Please rank how useful you consider the following modes of support in helping you learn GROMACS”

Looking at what learning resources new users to GROMACS encounter first of all when starting out, the small respondent cohort (only 8 users) who said they were just starting out learning to use GROMACS and had run less than 10 simulations ever were asked what resources they had used so far. The cohort only provided a small sample size, but tutorials were confirmed as an extremely important resource for learning how to use GROMACS. The GROMACS user manual and Beginner’s Guide were next most used, though some respondents were unaware of the existence of the Beginner’s Guide. The GROMACS “*Steps to perform a simulation*” guide was less used than might be expected, which may be due to a significant number of new users reporting not knowing it existed, suggesting it should be made more discoverable to new users. BioExcel webinars were hardly used by new users, and 50% did not know they existed.

GROMACS functionality

A number of questions were asked of experienced (expert and intermediate) users in order to help BioExcel, in particular the GROMACS development team, understand specific functionality used by users, whether this met their needs, and what was considered most desirable to be improved. Experienced users described regularly using the GROMACS functionalities shown in Figure 17.

D3.4 – User Community Support and Engagement Report (half-time update)

Figure 17: responses to the question “Which of the following GROMACS functionalities do you use regularly?”

The category “other” included, from expert users:

- *Polarizable simulations*
- *Essential Dynamics*
- *System preparation (editconf)*
- *PLUMED*

and from intermediate users:

- *Computational electrophysiology*
- *Alchemical code, vacuum simulations (group cutoffs!)*

Expert and intermediate users mostly agreed on their most regularly used GROMACS functionalities, with expert users being somewhat more likely to use most functionalities, especially replica exchange and potential of mean force calculations. QM/MM simulations and normal mode analysis on the other hand seemed to be used more by users with intermediate experience.

When asked to evaluate how well GROMACS performs in its provision of the above functionalities, including in comparison with other available software, experienced users responded as shown in Figure 18. There was remarkable consensus between the evaluations of expert and intermediate users. Energy minimisation - the most commonly used GROMACS functionality - was rated most highly on average. QM/MM simulations showed both the largest variability in rating between intermediate users and expert users, with the latter more likely to hold the opinion that GROMACS QM/MM functionality needs improvement, and the lowest overall rating. The work BioExcel is doing developing an interface between GROMACS and CP2K and supporting its usage through training, in-depth support, including the production of a best practice guide surrounding its usage seems especially well targeted in light of these results.

D3.4 – User Community Support and Engagement Report (half-time update)

Figure 18: responses to the question “Please rate the following based on whether you feel GROMACS excels at (is as good as or better than other available software), is OK at, or should improve at”

Free form optional comments addressing the question of GROMACS functionality supplied by respondents on this topic included:

From intermediate users:

- *As I am a very visual learner, I would love to be able to interact with the system via a viewer. Especially selecting (e.g. via `make_ndx`) without visual feedback is very counter-intuitive. More readily integrated analysis methods for ion channels would be amazing (pore detection,...).*
- *Could link MD to a QM scheme like SCCDFTB coded into the gromacs code*
- *Gromacs needs interface with Q-Chem for QM/MM. We use home-written one, but it would be much better to have one which is the part of official distribution and is fully supported by GROMACS team.*
- *GROMACS alone does not suffice for most of the free energy calculations. The GROMACS analysis modules are not general enough to be used for non-biomolecular systems. I write my own codes/scripts for that purpose.*
- *Simulation analysis - more detailed literature explaining what analysis commands do and examples would be very helpful*
- *Output formats of gmx analysis tools are outdated/old fashioned*
- *I use gmx tools for basic analysis, but often you need something more ad-hoc for my systems (which is fine)*
- *I wish the Normal Mode Analysis were as robust as suits such as ProDy, bio3d or similar*
- *Developers should develop a tool that calculates the free energy with MBAR method.*
- *Please please please re-add the ability to run vacuum simulations (non- periodic) in GROMACS again. Also, making the alchemical code faster would be great. And adding in additional order-parameters, such as the ones in PLUMED.*

From expert users:

- *I think QM/M and replica exchange are not so well documented. Some official tutorials would help a lot. A lot of analysis need improvements in performance. Coarse-grained users would benefit of more non-bonded potentials implemented with performance as good as LJ.*

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- *I've always found taking PMF calculations into WHAM yields a lot of files and a lot of time. Wouldn't it be cool if gromacs had its own ZIP file, which held the PMF umbrella trajectories and forces which could then be queried as and when needed. E.g., `getUmbrellaDistributions(PMFObject)`.. Etc.*
- *Free Energy Calculations can be more streamlined like including FEP+REST2 protocol in GROMACS. DFTB calculations similar to AMBER can also be implemented in GROMACS. Replica exchange tutorials can be written in a much better way. Simulation analysis can also be parallelised.*
- *Is QM/MM still being maintained?*
- *Free energy: user interface options are somewhat obscure at times and can often cause user errors replica exchange: needs newer algorithms like REST2 QM/MM: interface is not as simple & flexible as AMBER's*
- *Properly wrapping multi-protein complexes into the box for analysis is the most annoying part*

Improving GROMACS and its usage

In order to help BioExcel prioritise work developing and support GROMACS, experienced users were asked what single aspect they considered most important to improve when it came to functionality where they felt GROMACS needed improving (see Figure 19).

Figure 19: responses to the question “For those functionality where you feel GROMACS should improve, what is the single most important improvement?”

Intermediate users were most likely to consider improving ease of use to be top priority, and a larger proportion of them cared most about this and about improving documentation than expert users did. Expert users in contrast were most likely to consider improving available algorithms top priority, i.e. making a wider range of algorithms or algorithmic options available for those functionalities that users felt needed improving, which agreed with the second priority of intermediate users, and which was the top priority overall amongst all experienced users taken together.

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Respondents provided a number of useful free form optional comments addressing the question of GROMACS improvement:

From intermediate users:

- *For some functionality I would like to dive more into the manual but functions are not well documented. I sometimes feel I am using a black box*
- *Popular enhanced sampling methods need to be included. Current setups require patching with plumed but it also affects the performance. Integrating these algorithms in the native code would help in improving performance.*
- *The need for several command line steps (editconf?) is annoying but tolerable. The lack of a well-publicized set of "known good" settings for common-case MD (timestep, thermostat, groups...), not so much. It's understandable that it's research software, and people are supposed to know the ins and outs of their settings. However, the sheer number of combinations of settings calls for protocols for common cases, e.g. protein- only GPU production runs (even better if somehow validated). Without them, every group ends up cultivating their "traditional" settings and scripts, which is sub-optimal and error-prone.*
- *Implementation of efficient methods for polarisable force field seems essential, see eg openmm.*
- *Please have more easy to understand, step by step documentation like those by Justin Lemkul*
- *Interface with Q-Chem and advanced tools for spectroscopy modeling and QM/MM*
- *More examples of gmx commands usage would be helpful.*
- *Also, make the analysis modules more general so that they can be used for non-biomolecular systems.*
- *System generation is troublesome and sometimes irreproducible. pdb2gmx can generate systems with different energy values if for example atom groups are placed in different order. This is troublesome if conversion is needed of the pdb2gmx generated topology files to other formats. Pdb2gmx needs urgent rework and far more testing compared to the implementation of new MD algorithms. Pdb2gmx could benefit of the use of other open source libraries such as Parmed.*
- *The compatibility of thermostats and barostats with each other and with other mdp parameters could be broadened. I also would appreciate if you enable the use of the APPLE&P force field with Gromacs. Also an algorithm for constant potential simulations of systems with electrodes would be very helpful.*
- *Provide details on running simulations on clusters with multiple nodes*
- *Improvements could be made on how to troubleshoot also with more detailed error messages*
- *Annoying part of developing topologies when you have to add a new residue to the existing forcefield.*
- *Constant-pH. Metadynamics (native plumed) or other expanded/extended ensemble algorithms for free energy profiles*
- *Would be good to reduce reliance on other external sources/programs for certain applications (e.g. free energy calculations analysis using alchemical_analysis.py, system preparation using FESetup/BioSimSpace, MM/PBSA and MM/GBSA using g_mmpbsa, availability of forcefields such as Amberff14SB without wondering about correctness from user- contributions)*
- *I think it should be extended to support lone pairs in a more straight forward method like CHARMM*

From expert users:

- *I think QM/MM could also have more implementations. Coarse-grained users would benefit of more non-bonded potentials implemented with performance as good as LJ. All variety of Mie potentials would be great.*
- *Rational debugging with consistency checks and [...] testing*
- *Provide multiple time stepping to increase the time step in GROMACS. Provide Multiple time stepping for extended Lagrangian also in GROMACS. GROMACS should now be developed in tune with the PLUMED collective variable used, so that simulation doesn't crash easily.*
- *I think it would be good to discuss in more detail in official documentation the most widespread troubles of preparation and running simulations (e.g. gen-pairs directive, triclinic cells and -ur compact, EM and constraints errors, "there is no domain*

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decomposition" etc.). Usually some pieces of information may be found in mailing lists, but IMHO it is much worse than structured and detailed documentation.

- *Always strive to improve performance.*
- *GPU support for charge perturbation*
- *I'm aware that substantial effort is being made to make grompp better at picking up user errors, this would be my top priority, but since it's already in progress, more performance would always be better.*
- *I found most frustrated was to trying to use QM/MM with g09 or ORCA. There is simply no help or tutorials or examples to be found. Many documentations on the web are outdated.*
- *The addition of a multiple time-step algorithm(s) would be very advantageous.*
- *Ease of use, available algorithms and documentation are probably all linked. It can be difficult to work out which gmx tools can be used for certain analysis and sometimes you need roundabout routes. Maybe something like a wiki with examples as is done for pymol would help. I usually search the mail list for answers and occasionally RG these days comes up with useful comments.*
- *Please improve the documentation of analysis tools.*
- *Support of virtual sites for -update gpu. Better GPU acceleration support for free energy calculations.*
- *We need to simulate nonequilibrium simulation like LAMMPS, and also inorganic system like Steel-Oil.*
- *H-REMD for arbitrary TPRs a la PLUMED would be great, and I'm excited for AWH to become more flexible. I have found that GROMACS documentation is excellent.*
- *QM/MM with Gromacs and QM code needs a patch and is not straightforward*

Many of the above comments reflect user experiences with older versions of GROMACS and CP2K. BioExcel's work in this area indeed appears to be particularly well targeted in light of some of the comments and issues identified regarding the maturity of QM/MM functionality. These issues are being addressed by the Centre, including through development of:

- The QM/MM interface between GROMACS and CP2K
- Tutorials on QM/MM simulation of specific systems
- A Best Practice Guide on QM/MM simulation with GROMACS+CP2K using the BioExcel-developed interface
- A general GROMACS Best Practice Guide
- A Best Practice Guide on using PMX to perform alchemical free energy calculations

In order to ensure that BioExcel, especially the GROMACS development team, is driven by the needs of the user community in how best to spend available effort to develop the code, experienced users were asked to express their preference for the GROMACS team to prioritise improving performance of existing features versus adding new features. This was done by asking users to indicate on a scale from 0 (absolute preference for improving performance of current features) to 10 (absolute preference for addition of new features). Results are shown in Figure 20.

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Figure 20: responses to the question “Please rate how much you feel GROMACS developers should prioritise improving the performance of currently existing features over adding novel features to GROMACS”

Summing up prioritisation preferences for all experienced users (and splitting the neutral “5” equally to both sides), 42% prioritises improving performance and 58% prioritises new features. Summing for expert users gives the same result but closer to prioritising performance (48% vs 52%). For intermediate users a larger 63% is in favour of adding new features. These results appear to reflect the priorities identified in Figure 19.

When asked to similarly express their prioritisation preference for improving the ease of use of existing features versus performance, experienced users responded as shown Figure 21. All experienced users taken together expressed a 60% preference for improving performance of current features over 40% for improving ease of use. This was matched within a percent by both intermediate and expert cohorts, showing strong agreement. Whereas this prioritisation of performance improvement over ease of use improvement could be predicted for the expert user cohort given their evaluation of important improvements in Figure 19, this was the opposite of what would be expected on the same basis for intermediate users, who strongly thought ease of use was more important to improve than performance. However interestingly when forced to choose, e.g. due to limited available effort from the GROMACS developers, intermediate users were ultimately equally in favour of prioritising performance improvement rather than sacrificing this to obtain improvement in ease of use.

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Figure 21: responses to the question “Please rate how much you feel GROMACS developers should prioritise improving the ease of use of current features over the performance of these features”

GROMACS and other MD software

Other than GROMACS, experienced users also used MD software - see Figure 22.

Figure 22: responses to the question “Which, if any, other molecular dynamics programs do you use?”

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Broadly speaking the relative popularity of other MD packages was similar for all experienced GROMACS users. Many respondents (34%) only used GROMACS, with this being the case for more expert (40%) than intermediate GROMACS users (29%). However expert GROMACS users were more likely than intermediate users to also be using AMBER, OpenMM, Desmond, and DL_POLY. Conversely intermediate GROMACS users were very much more likely than expert GROMACS users to also use NAMD, and, with less start a difference also LAMMPS and CHARMM and finally Tinker.

Some free form comments were provided by intermediate users on other MD packages:

- *Have to use charmm as it has better QM/MM feature. Waiting for gromacs to pick this up*
- *I have used DL_POLY previously but when you gain an order of magnitude speedup, you go for that*

In order to help understand why users use other packages rather than GROMACS, experienced users were asked what, in their opinion, is the single most important thing that these other packages do better than GROMACS, which yielded the responses in Figure 23.

Figure 23: responses to the question “In your opinion, what is the single most important thing that these other programs do better than GROMACS?”

A significantly larger percentage (49%) of respondents than those who said in Figure 22 to only use GROMACS (34%) indicated there was no single feature of other MD packages that they could highlight as being better than GROMACS. No single specific aspect indicated by users as being better in other MD packages than GROMACS was said to be so by more than 15% of respondents, apart from 17% of intermediate users highlighting ease of use (almost double the expert user percentage). The next most noted aspect in which other MD programs do better

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than GROMACS was in performance, though even just less than 10% of expert and intermediate users mentioned this. Intermediate users were significantly more likely than expert users to think other packages make it easier to find information in documentation than GROMACS does, though this also amounted to under 10% of intermediate users.

A large number of informative free form comments representing the “other” response category were provided by respondents, reflective of a range of aspects they thought other MD packages did better than GROMACS.

From intermediate GROMACS users:

- *Better QM/MM support*
- *Scaling*
- *NAMD: implicit solvent; ACEMD: performance on GPU*
- *They have other applications which are missing in gromacs. Gromacs is the best MD software I had used in terms of speed or ease of use*
- *Support of polarizable force fields*
- *Supported forcefield*
- *The other programs are way better for normal modes analyses and techniques related.*
- *other algorithms*
- *Customisability*
- *More features e.g. AMBER allows you to parameterise small molecules, non- standard amino acids etc.*
- *Functionalities not available in gromacs*
- *python support in openMM*
- *More functionalities*
- *have functionality not available in gromacs*
- *Has a script to convert small molecules into gromacs format*
- *Easier setup for complex simulations (ligand/protein for instance)*
- *They support the different Force Fields.*
- *GROMACS tends to be too focused on bio simulations, i.e. wrestling things into residues is not so straightforward for materials systems*
- *I think Gromacs is overall easier and supports more features than Lammmps. CHARMM has a lot of features/functions that Gromacs doesn't have*
- *They have algorithms and potentials not available in GROMACS (i.e. polarizable force-fields, 14-7 VDW interactions etc)*

And, from expert GROMACS users:

- *They have other methods implemented. For instance, NAMD has ABF and accelerated MD, which are easy to use*
- *Correctness*
- *It is much easier to setup complex systems in CHARMM and analyze custom properties. GROMACS is limited to built-in analysis functions, which is restrictive (though the tools are good). pdb2gmx is severely limiting.*
- *Functionalities like EVB*
- *Provides some methods not available in GROMACS*
- *I only use other programs if they implement something GROMACS doesn't (e.g. polarisable model, etc.)*
- *Availability of reliable forcefields quickly - for instance, parmbsc1 for DNA*
- *I love openMM because it is implemented into a python environment*
- *Sometimes I find the grid potential very useful. Though I seem to remember GROMACS now also has it?*
- *The source-code is more readable and therefore easier to edit*
- *They have features that are unavailable in GROMACS. Constant pH MD, for instance*
- *I used AMBER because SIRAH implementation in GROMACS is different and might have an issue*

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- *Availability of specific method (accelerated MD)*
- *Amber have a proper QM/MM interface*
- *LAMMPS and DL_POLY have more functionality - for example more forms of potential. They are also easier to modify in house.*
- *In the past, I worked with proteins in implicit solvent. AMBER provides an easy way to build proteins by hand and has much more support for implicit solvent systems. Not as important to me nowadays.*
- *More appropriate for specific simulation methods, such as QM/MM or continuum calculation*
- *Probably best PLUMED support, also good performance, although hard to tune*
- *Easy to add new features*
- *Other functionality, such as EVB or QM/MM*

Conclusions & follow up

The GROMACS survey provided useful insights into the needs of existing users with varying degrees of experience, and have confirmed the value of work done so far in the project, such as the development of a QM/MM interface to CP2K, and the production of various tutorials, planned best practice guides, and training. Survey findings confirm some existing prioritisations within the GROMACS development roadmap, and are helping guide adjustment of some of these.

Out of the survey respondents, 16 expert users, 19 intermediate, 8 novice, and 2 new users volunteered to be interviewed one-on-one to capture further in-depth insights to ensure BioExcel is user driven.

Hybrid QM/MM Molecular Modelling & Simulation (GROMACS+CP2K)

Community participation

The JYU team has given the following talks at meetings and workshops to present QM/MM molecular modelling results and engage the academic community

- Presented at the “*Summer School and Workshop in Multiscale Modelling*” at Lorentz Center in Leiden, Netherlands, June 24-28, 2019
- Demonstration of the CP2K code and QM/MM use case examples in “*Introduction to CP2K*” at the *BioExcel Summer School on Biomolecular Simulations* at Science and Technology Park of Sardinia, Pula, Italy, June 30 - July 5, 2019.
- Presentation at the “*17th International Congress on Photobiology*” in Barcelona, Spain, August 25-30, 2019.
- Presentation at the “*Finnish Computational Chemistry Days*” organised at University of Eastern Finland, Kuopio, Finland, August 29-30, 2019.
- Presentation at the “*Frontiers in Multiscale Modelling of Photoreceptor Protein*”, CECAM workshop organised at The Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Israel, September 3-5, 2019.
- Presentation at “*9th International Symposium on Photochromism*” organised at Institut Pasteur, Paris, France, September 23-27, 2019.

The work of the UEDIN team in BioExcel focuses to a large extent on optimising CP2K and providing support and training in its usage for biomolecular QM/MM simulation, in particular in conjunction with the project’s newly developed GROMACS-CP2K interface. As CP2K is the only core BioExcel application whose core development team is not directly involved in the project, UEDIN has been forging links with this core development team as well as those “power user” researchers using CP2K for its traditional non-biomolecular applications who are involved in fostering the broad CP2K user community in the UK. To facilitate this, UEDIN attended and discussed BioExcel’s work at the 2019 *CP2K Users and Developers Meeting* that took place June 14th at Imperial College London. Possibilities for joint activities with these researchers surrounding CP2K training and academic exchange relating to QM/MM were discussed.

UEDIN has provided a 3-day training course, “*Introduction to HPC for Life Scientists*”, which included a QM/MM practical component using CP2K, and the course was used as an opportunity to engage with a number of researchers interested in using QM/MM for biomolecular simulation or intending to do so, and to both advertise and seek input on BioExcel’s activities, such as development of the QM/MM interface with GROMACS.

The UEDIN team has also forged connections with the UK-based computational biomolecular simulation community, in particular the relevant ARCHER national HPC service user consortium [HECBioSim](#) and the national research council-funded

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Collaborative Computational Project for Biomolecular Simulation - [CCP-BioSim](#). This community has researchers actively using QM/MM simulation and biomolecular simulators interested in starting to use QM/MM, and these were amongst those engaged in a large online QM/MM community survey reported on in this section. CCP-BioSim and BioExcel plan to organise joint training and academic exchange in 2021. UEDIN attendance was planned at the [April 2020 CCP-BioSim Multiscale conference](#), in particular at a [training workshop on ChemShell](#), software which amongst other things provides a way to couple MD and QM codes to perform QM/MM simulation, similar to the BioExcel-1 developed MiMiC coupling between GROMACS and CPMD and BioExcel's current GROMACS-CP2K coupling. This would have been an opportunity to engage in person with computational biomolecular researchers interested in QM/MM in order to better understand their research software needs so as to feed this into GROMACS-CP2K interface development and support of its usage, and also to contribute by sharing and promoting BioExcel's work. It would also have provided an opportunity to discuss with ChemShell developers and power users software engineering challenges specific to QM/MM. Unfortunately this event was cancelled due to COVID-19.

With regards to community participation, UEDIN is therefore connecting BioExcel with the core CP2K development team, with CP2K power users in the code's traditional non-biomolecular application areas, and crucially with biomolecular researchers interested in performing QM/MM simulation and those already doing so.

Best Practices in Computational Quantum Chemistry for Biomolecules

Planning is underway in BioExcel through the joint action of QM/MM partners JYU, UEDIN and FZJ to organise a meeting in Q4 of 2020 on "*Best Practices in Computational Quantum Chemistry for Biomolecules*", which is meant to address two key challenges faced by (new) users of QM/MM for biomolecular simulation.

The first challenge revolves around choosing an adequate computational QM treatment (theory level and parameterisation, e.g. choice of functional and basis set for DFT) for their biomolecular system of interest that is based on a reasoned understanding of the accuracy and limitations of the chosen approach in light of what is known about the underlying quantum chemistry. Many inexperienced practitioners use default or common choices and hope for the best, or refer to previously published work as justification for adequacy even though they are treating a system with substantially distinct underlying quantum chemistry.

The second challenge is to choose a suitable reaction coordinate (and with it a suitable method to sample/minimize the system along that coordinate) in the high-dimensional configuration space of a typical (bio)chemical system. Reducing the space to a chemically meaningful set of reaction coordinates again requires a deep understanding of the underlying chemistry.

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The discussions that really matter with regards to choosing the QM approach for biomolecular QM/MM and/or defining suitable reaction coordinates are the ones that have been ongoing in the computational chemistry community for decades. These difficulties hinder the successful exploitation of QM/MM simulation, and are a prior consideration to what particular software package or combination of packages is used.

The goals of the meeting are to exchange, develop and capture best practices in computational biomolecular quantum chemistry and to disseminate these through documented guidance and through training and support to researchers using - or intending to use - QM/MM for biomolecular simulation.

The meeting aims to get together expert / active users of QM/MM and possibly (theoretical) QM method developers rather than beginning users (it is not a training event). Software developers may be invited, but software development is not intended to be the main topic of the meeting.

In-depth support

Users have been supported with QM/MM related questions on the GROMACS user list and forum. In response to difficulties encountered setting up QM/MM simulations, a number of users were provided with a workflow for QM/MM simulations of fluorescent proteins. This workflow is being extended and is planned for release in Q3 2020 along with a publication demonstrating results that can be achieved.

Researchers at Imperial College in London were supported in their femtosecond X-ray crystallography experiments on reversibly photoswitchable fluorescent proteins (rsFP). In collaboration with a group from KU Leuven, pilot simulations were carried out on new rsFP mutants with an initial aim to predict the effect of mutations on the folding, the absorption maxima, and the Stokes shift. In addition, a group from Cardiff University have been supported by providing both classical and QM/MM simulation parameters for the fluorescent proteins.

[Two tutorials](#) describing how to perform QM/MM simulation for biomolecular systems were produced and made available. Tutorials of this kind, namely detailed concrete step by step “How To” recipes that can be followed by users and adapted to their particular problem/system, were identified in the online QM/MM community survey reported later in this section as the single most valuable form of training/support according to the largest number of users, surpassing even the perceived value by users of direct in-depth advice on a support forum. BioExcel also improved a tutorial/How To hosted on the official CP2K website that is typically the first resource any user interested in using CP2K to perform biomolecular QM/MM simulation comes across, learns from, and adapts to their own research question. The impact of these improvements is difficult to gauge, but strong evidence from the QM/MM survey as well as anecdotal evidence from users support the popularity and importance of these concrete tutorials, suggesting that this significantly supports the community.

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A researcher at the University of Edinburgh heading a nascent group interested in using QM/MM simulation was provided in-depth support using CP2K to simulate peptides. This support activity is due to feed into the generation of a tutorial specifically requested by the researcher to train and support new group members as well as provide a foundation for further research. It will also feed into an additional public BioExcel QM/MM benchmark and provide experience to draw on for the production of a GROMACS+CP2K best practice guide (see “Standards and best practice” below).

Standards and best practice

An installation guide was documented for the new GMX+CP2K QM/MM interface and shared with multiple users based on direct contact.

An analysis module was generated and added to the best practice guide for the workflow targeting free energy calculations, molecular dynamics trajectories, and QM/MM calculations of green fluorescent proteins (GFPs).

Planning was concluded for a best practice guide on usage of GROMACS+CP2K for QM/MM simulation to be produced by UEDIN covering key simulation steps, a checklist, common pitfalls, etc. The guide will gather together expertise gained within BioExcel by running a range of prepared, curated, and documented QM/MM benchmarks provided in a benchmark suite released publicly by the project starting with an initial release as part of deliverable D1.4 - Project release of core applications.

Online community QM/MM survey

To ensure the work done by BioExcel is user driven, an online survey was conducted in the biomolecular simulation community to better understand the needs of researchers with regards to QM/MM simulation and the usage of relevant software. The survey targeted researchers both experienced and inexperienced in the use of QM/MM simulation and sought to identify their needs for training and support as well as software functionality and performance. The survey also aimed to gauge the strength and nature of interest amongst researchers for participating in community events focusing on QM/MM simulation of biomolecular systems, including research sharing oriented meetings (workshops, symposia, etc.) and events incorporating training, which BioExcel could organise.

The goal of the survey was to provide clear views of the barriers encountered by (potential) users of QM/MM simulation, including how these relate to the software packages being used and the research topics and types of biomolecular systems being studied. The findings confirm that the work done by BioExcel is set to meet unmet community needs, in particular in relation to developing and supporting usage of the project’s core QM/MM applications GROMACS and CP2K, and have helped steer work due to take place during the second half of the project. The

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survey also functioned as a way to alert interested researchers in the GROMACS-CP2K interface due to be released and to highlight that support could be sought from BioExcel in its usage (and indeed in usage of CP2K alone). A separate online community survey focusing on GROMACS also yielded some insights into community needs relevant to QM/MM executed jointly with GROMACS and CP2K. These can be found in the analysis reported in the “GROMACS Online Community Survey” subsection of the “Classical Molecular Modelling and Simulation” section of this deliverable.

Respondent backgrounds

The survey received 127 responses, majoritarily from academia, broken down as shown in Figure 24.

Figure 24: responses to the question “Which of the following best describes you?”

Responses to the survey were representative of a range of levels of self-described general experience and expertise in biomolecular simulation, as evidenced by the responses shown in Figure 25.

Figure 25: responses to the question “How would you rate your overall expertise in computational simulation of biomolecular systems using molecular dynamics, QM/MM, or other approaches?”

With regards to experience using QM/MM specifically, the respondents included a large number of currently active or previously successful users of QM/MM as well as somewhat smaller numbers of researchers who had tried using QM/MM but encountered significant issues and researchers who had not yet tried using QM/MM but were considering doing so, as shown in Figure 26.

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Figure 26: responses to the question “Do you use QM/MM simulation in your research?”

Systems studied

Biomolecular systems or system constituents reported as being studied by respondents actively using QM/MM or having previously done so successfully (the “experienced” QM/MM users), are shown in Figure 27.

Figure 27: responses to the question “What specific types of systems/constituents do you study? (check all that apply)”. Results show the absolute number of responses for each option in bold followed by what percentage of total responses to the question this corresponds to.

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Amongst these experienced QM/MM practitioners the proportions studying enzymes (78%), protein complexes (57%), peptides (43%), and metalloproteins (41%) were greatest (ignoring the less informative “proteins” category). Amongst respondents who had attempted to use QM/MM but encountered insurmountable barriers blocking success, there were even higher proportions studying protein complexes (73%) and peptides (58%), but lower proportions studying enzymes (49%) and metalloproteins (27%). Amongst inexperienced practitioners considering using QM/MM for the first time, enzymes remained near the top yet were studied by only 38% of respondents whilst interest in protein complexes (50%) and peptides (53%), which were most studied, remained strong, and metalloproteins (18%) were significantly less studied.

These findings appeared to indicate a pent up demand and potential growth area in QM/MM simulation of peptides and protein complexes that BioExcel might unlock if it were to meet unmet needs, which further analysis of the survey helped identify. It was clear that BioExcel should also seek to support particularly strong existing usage of QM/MM in enzymology and metalloprotein simulation, as well as in a range of other types of systems studied somewhat less frequently using QM/MM identified above.

Research topics

Asking respondents what research topics they were investigating yielded results in line with BioExcel expertise and interest, including use case work done in the project, as shown in Figure 28.

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Figure 28: responses to the question “What topics do you investigate? (check all that apply)”

Computed quantities & properties

Respondents were also asked to provide information about the physical / chemical quantities or properties they are interested in computing in order to enable BioExcel to more closely understand the functionality they require in QM/MM software and what kind of training tutorials and support would be required - see Figure 29.

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Figure 29: responses to the question “What properties are you interested in computing? (check all that apply)”

Software used

In order to determine the relevance of BioExcel code development, training, support, and other work targeting usage of CP2K including in conjunction with GROMACS, respondents who had experience performing QM/MM simulations - or trying to, be it successfully or not - were asked what software they had used. Responses are shown in Figure 30.

GAUSSIAN, the most commonly used quantum chemistry application, which had been used at some point by almost 60% of these respondents, is commercial software. The next most commonly used quantum chemistry package was CP2K, which 32% of respondents had used. The most common molecular dynamics application was GROMACS, which 50% of respondents had used, compared to the next most used, AMBER, at 44%. As much as 94% of respondents without any QM/MM experience had used GROMACS, whilst 44% had used GAUSSIAN and 32% had used AMBER (but neither package to perform QM/MM simulation).

Notwithstanding the possibility of (self) selection biases in sampling the community who chose to respond to the survey, these figures at the very least confirm that the findings throughout the rest of the survey and the work done by BioExcel in response are relevant to users already familiar with CP2K and/or GROMACS.

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Figure 30: responses to the question “What software have you used or tried to use to perform QM/MM simulations? (check all that apply)”

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Barriers

All respondents were asked which of a set of predefined issues had significantly hindered their use of QM/MM - see Figure 31.

Figure 31: responses to the question “Which of the following issues have significantly hindered your (attempted) use of QM/MM? Consider slowed progress, partial or lower quality results, or even failure to obtain any reliable or meaningful results. (check all that apply)”

Findings from this question provided insight into an array of needs that have driven BioExcel’s work. The largest single barrier to successful use of QM/MM according to 59% of respondents is the availability and/or quality of relevant practical tutorials. We interpreted this as a need for software usage tutorials containing concrete instructions that demonstrate how to perform all necessary steps in a given process relevant to QM/MM simulation, which can be followed by a user and adapted to solve their own related research question. In response, BioExcel has focused on producing QM/MM tutorials that can be used both in training events and to support self study.

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The availability and/or quality of software documentation was seen as an important barrier by 48% of respondents. BioExcel is tackling this by producing guidance on performing QM/MM simulations that capture best practice and supplement the CP2K manual in particular.

Another important barrier identified was deciding how to choose suitable QM parameters, which combines the fundamental issue of how to model the quantum chemistry of interactions in a particular system with sufficient accuracy with the concrete question of how to use a particular software application to do so in simulation. The BioExcel tutorials and best practice guide mentioned above address the latter. The former is a challenging topic, and on this front BioExcel is working to provide generic guidance on avoiding common pitfalls. The project is also planning to bring together experts to exchange knowledge and experiences regarding best practices in computational quantum chemistry for biomolecules and to capture and document these to provide guidance to less experienced simulators.

Software incompatibility, e.g. between MD and QM software - listed by 49% of respondents as a barrier - is being addressed by BioExcel through the usage-driven development of the GROMACS-CP2K interface, and performance is being addressed through optimisation work aimed at improving performance and scaling of CP2K including in conjunction with GROMACS. Software availability, licensing, and cost is addressed by BioExcel by virtue of GROMACS and CP2K being freely available and tested by BioExcel, PRACE, and other efforts on a large variety of compute platforms. Documentation and the GROMACS+CP2K best practice guide being produced by BioExcel are set to address other concerns raised, such as difficulty installing software and knowing how best to make use of computing resources.

A selection of free form comments by respondents gave further insights into their needs and issues they encountered making use of QM/MM:

- *There is a real lack of good quality tutorials out there for QM/MM and those that exist often use a very quick methodology to get the answer which isn't particularly scientifically sound. Fuller and complete tutorials (e.g. the Lemkul tutorials for Gromacs) would be a massive help.*
- *Bring us something that is easy to handle. Must contain tutorials and sample input which are easy and descriptive*
- *Documentation/tutorials sometimes scarce*
- *Most time consuming blocker is the "set-up" i.e. generating forcefield, list of qm atoms, active atoms etc.*
- *I think a good interface should be modular and with a clear API so the users can easily interface additional QM code to Gromacs with minimal modifications. I think it is best to allow the user to set the QM calculations interacting directly with the QM program*
- *I tried to work with cp2k and amber and tried its QM/MM tutorial but could not finish. Also I am using cp2k for the first time, its inputs and manual was very difficult to understand. Plus how should I couple both cp2k and AMBER as I am using it for the first time it is difficult for me to integrate both. I need tutorial for this*
- *Difficult to get excited state properties of the QM part of the system*
- *Availability of long range electrostatics (e.g. PME) and PBC is crucial for doing QM/MM MD for charged molecules freely diffusing in water. Also, we need exchange of water between QM and MM regions.*
- *Setting up the system is not easy either!*

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- *The absence of easy to use software for the assembly of heterogeneous quantum systems. The absence of the opportunity to change the composition of the QM region on the fly.*

Training and support

When asked what types/topics of training and support would most help respondents make use of QM/MM in their research, responses again emphasised concrete examples to be of most value - see Figure 32.

Figure 32: responses to the question “In which of the following areas would additional training & support most help you make (better) use of QM/MM in your research?”

Many of the other listed training and support topics were also identified as valuable, and this identification has fed into the planning of training and documentation of best practice guidance that BioExcel is producing. A follow-on question asking about preferences for formats of training and support confirmed again the perceived value of concrete tutorials - see Table 4.

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<i>Format</i>	<i>“Very useful”</i>	<i>“Somewhat useful”</i>
Tutorial consisting of a concrete ‘how to’ recipe for simulating a particular system using particular software	86%	12%
In-depth troubleshooting advice via a support forum	64%	34%
In-person training course including lectures & practicals	60%	34%
Online interactive demonstrations / participatory practicals	44%	46%
Webinar (with opportunity to ask questions)	38%	48%

Table 4: User preferences for QM/MM training and support formats

QM/MM community event

When asked whether respondents would be interested in attending a community event (workshop/symposium/mini-conference) focused on exchanging methodologies and results using QM/MM methodologies for biomolecular simulation with other researchers, 55% responded “very interested”, and 40% “interested”.

Additionally, roughly half of respondents provided optional free form comments when asked what would make them most likely to attend a QM/MM-focused community event. A selection of the most informative is included below, and these provide valuable input for event planning:

- *Discussion beyond single-point QM/MM calculations and enthalpy. Use of enhanced-sampling techniques to obtain FES, entropic contribution calculation, kinetics temperature dependence, KIE, mechanism-agnostic calculations, derivation of collective variables.*
- *Protein activity mechanism*
- *Share scientific ideas and methodological issues. In other words, to exchange successful studies and discuss problems that we all have to deal with when using QM/MM with biological systems*
- *Hands-on experience, 5 days at least, anywhere, anytime*
- *Online would be great. Speakers from GROMACS and Amber.*
- *If the event will take place somewhere in Europe. With the emphasis on the biomolecular simulations: enzymatic reactions, metal coordination in proteins, and other similar topics. A couple of days would be an excellent duration.*
- *Talks by the creators of the software, explaining the logic of the code, how to use it and best practices. Also, where the code needs to be improved.*
- *Biomolecular reaction and binding affinity. 3 days.*
- *European location, speakers who develop methods as well as users of methods talking about examples of use, results. Maybe some hands-on session with tutorials*
- *Variety of QM/MM experiences and applications in participants. Such an event is NOT interesting if everyone is doing the same thing, whatever is currently popular. Different points of view are interesting. 1-2 real experts should be available to doublecheck the QM/MM “recipes” of participants for their applications are sound and valid.*
- *QM/MM treatment of receptor ligand binding regions*
- *Knowledge of what regions or moieties of chemistry in biological systems require QM treatment and which can suffice only with MM.*

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- *Meeting software developers, from GMX etc.*
- *Since I have never used QM/MM, at the moment I would only be interested in beginner level tutorials*
- *European workshop targeting the well-known QM/MM failures and required improvements*
- *Topic: Use of QM/MM for reaction kinetics. Preferring workshop for those wanting to start QM/MM instead of targeting the researchers who already use QM/MM*
- *Speakers need to be experienced users, not only have theoretical knowledge*
- *Summer schools would be best with practice sessions*
- *The biggest factor in my attendance of such an event would be fitting into my schedule. Duration a day/half-day would probably be most likely to make me attend.*
- *Preferably in UK for a week about using GROMACS with CP2K*
- *Location easily reachable by train. Variety in use of software (and applications) of the speakers. Include (range of) enzyme reaction modelling*
- *Speakers from diverse backgrounds, multiple potential applications presented & advances in the field*
- *Molecular dynamics, working with unnatural amino acids, with metal in proteins*
- *Mostly interested in photochemistry/photophysics than for example enzymatic catalysis*
- *An overview of QM/MM functionality in MD software in Europe for no longer than 3 days would be great with experts in the field*
- *QM/MM for enzyme catalysis, especially involving hands-on tutorials and workshops. I believe 3 days of hands-on would be a good start, with additional materials for further studies.*
- *Desirable Topic: QM/MM study in metalloproteins and Protein-Drug complex Location: Germany, Sweden. Duration: 3 days (10 am to 4 pm sessions)*
- *Topics: excited states, most accurate/efficient approaches to free energy methods Location: any easily accessible city in Europe Duration: 3-4 days.*
- *Speaker to include experts in the field but also postdocs/PhD students who are relatable to beginners and can share their experience on how best to get started. Event duration should be 1-3 days. Desirable topics would include application to clinical research and drug discovery.*
- *Topics: Protein-protein (or DNA) interactions. Non-covalent interactions*
- *Enhanced sampling with QM/MM*
- *Molecular modelling and drug design using QM/MM.*
- *QM calculations and their interpretation*
- *Topics of interest in reaction mechanisms or enzymes*
- *Setting up QM/MM simulation and integrating QM and MM software to run a simulation.*
- *Coordinated water structures around organic molecules (proteins, nucleic acids)*
- *Good, central European location. Ideally 2-3 days with opportunity for practicals. Good introductory tutorials as applied to systems.*

Conclusions

The QM/MM survey yielded valuable insights into existing areas to support, and potential growth areas. Strong community needs for practical tutorials were identified, and followed up on. Findings relating to training and research-sharing events are feeding into event planning.

Workflow Tools & Standards (CWL and biobb)

Community participation

The importance of reproducibility, interoperability and portability of biomolecular simulation workflows has always been one of the main objectives in BioExcel. The BioExcel building blocks (biobb) library, published in [Nature Scientific Data](#), pushed for the FAIR principles applied to software development. The biobb library has reached a mature level and has started to be used in different training and dissemination events (e.g. [Introduction to Simulation Environments for Life Sciences](#)), with good feedback from the participants (see user survey section). A [Virtual Training](#) entitled “*Computational biomolecular simulation workflows with BioExcel building blocks*” was also run successfully. It was run on two days, with 3h for each session, which allowed the attendees to work on some exercises in between; we had particularly good feedback, and the participants were asking for an extra day to be able to go deeper into the HPC workflows using the biobb library.

During the process of designing and defining these different training events, a set of Jupyter Notebook workflows were developed and made available through the [biobb website](#). Since the first feedback from the 2019 events, a set of [installation tutorials](#) was included (Q1 2020). Library versatility tutorials were also prepared and included in the website to showcase the possibility of using the library with different workflow managers and infrastructures. The tutorials site is designed to be a live site, with continuous update, and new demonstration tutorials are being added.

The biobb library is going to be presented at the [2020 \(Virtual\) BioExcel Summer School](#), and new events to make the library more visible and engage with our community are planned for the Q3 or Q4 of 2020: a biobb-focused webinar and a new, extended edition of the Virtual Training.

Another Virtual Training to demonstrate the importance of reproducibility, interoperability, and portability of biomolecular simulation workflows was run in April 2020, focused in this case on the [Common Workflow Language](#) (CWL).

In-depth support

Support on the biobb library users has been conducted mainly via private e-mails and resolving GitHub issues. The amount of questions and feedback received increased notably just after the different training events were completed. Quite surprisingly, questions from beginner-level users interested in starting with Molecular Dynamics simulations are still regularly answered via the MDWeb [ask.bioexcel forum section](#) (and also through direct e-mail communication), in spite of this tool being more than 10 years old now. All answers contain a short invitation to have a look at the work done in BioExcel, especially the biobb library and the associated Jupyter Notebook demonstration tutorials, which are much more powerful and updated than the mentioned web server. A new biobb-focused section on the ask.bioexcel forum was then generated, so that this already existent community of beginner-level users could start posting experiences and questions about the library.

Standards and best practice

The BioExcel building blocks (biobb) library, published in [Nature Scientific Data](#), pushed for the FAIR principles applied to software development, and the collection of installation and demonstration tutorials integrated in the biobb website show the possibilities of the packaging and containerization of software. All demonstration workflows generated in BioExcel are registered in the European bioinformatics registry [bio.tools](#), with proper links to the source code (BioExcel GitHub), Read the Docs documentation, and, when possible, to MyBinder and the BioExcel Cloud Portal to directly test them or try them out. All building blocks are described with CWL. All workflows, demonstration tutorials, and complex scientific workflows will be registered in the [workflow hub](#), the EOSC-Life repository, and a registry of computational workflows for data analysis, once available.

User surveys

In 2019, we organized the workshop *“PATC simulation in life sciences environments”*. The user survey evidenced that more time has to be dedicated to the hands-on training and actively engaging the participants. For this reason, in the PATC workshop organized in 2020, we introduced hands-on Jupyter notebook workflows for the set up and the production of molecular dynamics simulation in a GPU-based BSC supercomputer (Minotauro). In this way, the hands-on was more complete and the participants were more actively engaged. In the follow-up survey we got very positive comments about the hands-on and the users noted a *“very appropriate level for inexperienced MD simulation users. The Jupyter notebook to set up the simulation is extremely useful in this sense. Also the contextualization was really good to structure the awareness on what is being done and what can be done.”*

Industry

(CONFIDENTIAL section, available to authorized parties upon request)

Conclusions and future work

BioExcel is meeting and exceeding stretch targets on all WP3 KPIs (number of community members supported and from whom input has been gathered, tutorials made available to users, and questions answered on the AskBioExcel forum). The Centre has delivered substantial amounts of support, especially to a well-established and ever growing user base corresponding to the core applications GROMACS, PMX and HADDOCK. The execution of free energy calculations by combining functionalities of GROMACS and PMX has been confirmed during BioExcel-2 through surveys, in-depth discussions, and the popularity of in-person events such as the BioExcel-organised *Alchemical Free Energy Workshop 2019* and a webinar on this topic as an area of very strong interest from both academia and industry. Requests for support are accordingly high, and a pilot project with industry is being approached carefully so as not to exceed available effort and expertise within the Centre. In addition measures are being taken to support the community in a scalable way by producing tutorials and a best practice guide. In the longer term, though expertise and effort may be somewhat constrained within this area currently, at least so as not to interfere with other project activities, the high pent-up demand suggests opportunities exist for a BioExcel Legal Entity to sustain itself in part by focusing on meeting this demand. Workflow tools also play a role, as the containerised execution of large numbers of free energy calculations orchestrated by the PyCOMPSs execution engine to efficiently make use of large-scale parallel HPC resources are enabling rapid massive screening of therapeutics on HPC platforms. As the Use Case work using these tools progresses, the Centre will be able to further leverage the capability demonstrating work done there to support the wider community make use of these tools to perform large-scale free energy calculations.

In contrast to GROMACS, PMX and HADDOCK, there is still not a large user base in existence that actively uses CP2K for biomolecular simulation using the hybrid QM/MM approach. BioExcel is providing live training sessions and creating, improving and updating tutorials that users can study by themselves to get started using CP2K for QM/MM simulation of biomolecular systems, and is in the process of producing a best practice guide. With regards to the GROMACS-CP2K interface, this is now at a maturity level where it can start to be used for Use Case work as planned in the original BioExcel-2 project timeline. CP2K is simultaneously being optimised for scaling and performance and the interface tested, with work underway to discover and document best practice for joint usage of GROMACS together with CP2K for performing QM/MM simulation. In the second half of BioExcel-2, the Centre will draw on this experience to support and train the

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community. In addition to training plans, events are also being planned to help stimulate uptake of CP2K (+GROMACS) for biomolecular research using QM/MM simulation. This is being done by tackling both the hurdle of arriving at a scientifically valid, accuracy-controlled QM treatment of a user's system using DFT, and issues surrounding usage of CP2K's particular implementation of a given DFT approach and how to concretely use the software to obtain meaningful results in an efficient manner, with or without GROMACS.

Surveys of GROMACS and QM/MM user communities have yielded insights that have already helped shape support activities such as the content of best practice guides, and they will continue to do so. Survey results are feeding into development work, both by direct identification of feature and performance priorities and, in the case of CP2K, by ensuring that the QM/MM benchmarks used to profile and improve the code's performance and parallel scaling include a range of system types, sizes, and model parameters that are representative of the priorities of the user community. Further survey work may also help identify additional opportunities for the Centre to facilitate uptake of workflow tools such as the BioExcel building blocks (bioBB) and the PyCOMPSs execution manager, which in a number of BioExcel Use Cases are key to enabling efficient exploitation of large-scale computing resources to demonstrate how to tackle grand scientific challenges.

APPENDIX

Event feedback report for BioExcel Alchemical Free Energy Workshop 2019

General

- 66% of workshop attendees filled in the survey, i.e. 76 out of 115 attendees.
- 33% of surveys were filled in online, 67% were in paper format.
- Participant distribution = 79% academic, 21% industry

Figure 33: Type of participant

Figure 34: Overall meeting rating (75% said Excellent or Very Good)

Figure 35: Scope of the meeting rating (74% said just right or slightly too narrow)

GROMACS usage

- 50% of survey participants use GROMACS (in combination) for FE calculations. The percentage of GROMACS users is higher if you include those that use ‘Multiple’ tools, of which GROMACS is one.
- 37% of survey participants stated they used GROMACS/pmx in combination.
- 10% of survey participants did not state which software they used for FE calculations.

Figure 36: Software usage for free energy calculations

- Survey participants who use GROMACS (in combination) provide the following main reasons for doing so; Familiarity/Historical reasons (38%), Free (21%), Ease of use (18%), Performance/Quality (13%). 24% did not provide a reason.

Industry users

- 32% of industry scientists surveyed use GROMACS (in combination). This percentage increases if you include those that use ‘Multiple’ tools, of which GROMACS is one.
- The top reason provided by industry scientists for using GROMACS was Familiarity.
- 25% of industry scientists surveyed use Maestro/FEP+.
- The top reason provided by industry scientists for using Maestro/FEP+ was Ease of use.

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Figure 37: Industry researcher use of GROMACS (legend colours match software packages as in Figure 36).

- 7 out of 16 industry scientists (44%) requested an on-site visit but no field was provided to capture contact details.

Additional satellite event

- 66% of survey participants wanted an additional satellite hands-on practical before/after the meeting.
- The most popular topics for a satellite hands-on practical fell broadly into the following categories:
 - Setup (best practices, enhanced setup) = 25%
 - Demos (academic and industrial, merits of each) = 18%
 - Applications = 15%
 - Workflows = 12%
 - Advances (tools, new tech) = 12%
 - Intro and tutorials = 12%
 - Use cases (inc. failures) = 6%

Additional topics for future BioExcel events

- 42% of survey participants provided a view on additional topics for future BioExcel events.
- The most popular topics for future events fell broadly into the below categories. Some of these topics overlap with those for a satellite event.
 - Advanced topics (Machine Learning, enhanced sampling and Metadynamics were by far the most popular advanced topics highlighted) = 50%
 - Protein-protein & protein-ligand (simulations, conformations, drug discovery) = 23%

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- Other FE methods = 8%
- Errors, tips, applications, caveats = 8%
- Good practices & methods development = 8%
- Workflows = 3%
- Meeting recurrence = 78% Every Year (one year in EU, one year in US)

Figure 38: Preferred recurrence frequency for a similar free energy meeting

- >80% of participants would pay €100 or more to register.
- Almost 40% of participants would pay €150-200 to register.

Figure 39: Willingness of attendees to pay fees to attend a similar free energy meeting